

MINISTRY OF HEALTH PROTECTION OF UKRAINE

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THE ROLE OF THE NEUROENDOCRINE-IMMUNE COMPLEX IN THE
MECHANISM OF ACTION OF
BALNEOTHERAPY (experimental and clinical studies)

14.03.04 - pathological physiology

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Official opponents:

GENERAL CHARACTERISTICS OF THE RESEARCH

Actuality of theme. The human body is a supersystem, and therefore his Adaptation reactions in normal and pathological conditions are always complex and include both specific and numerous non-specific reactions [A.I. Gozhenko, 2015]. To the most important non-specific reactions include reactions of the neuroendocrine immune complex. Since the

epoch-making discovery of H. Selye [1936], it is known that it is non-specific the pathogenetic basis of many chronic diseases is stress (general adaptation syndrome). This concept is developed by its numerous followers [Horizontov P.D. and others, 1983; Meerson F.Z., 1986, 1993; L.H. Garkavy and others, 1990, 1998; Chrousos GP, 1992-2005; Stress of Life, 1998; O.M. Radchenko, 2004; Reznikov O.G. et al., 2004; Dhabhar FS, 2009-2018; Baraboy V.A., Reznikov O.G., 2013; Reznikov O.G., 2019].

Physiological antipode of stressors are adaptogens, which act stress-limiting effect by induction of anti-stress general adaptation reactions The level of resistance of the organism is determined by the quality of its general adaptation reaction [L.H. Harkavy and others, 1990, 1998; O.M. Radchenko, 2004]. By L.H. Garkavy et al. [1990], all stimuli and influences should be considered adaptogens (electric stimulation of the hypothalamus, carbon dioxide as an irritant reticular formation and interoreceptors, magnetic fields, neurotropic agents, immunomodulators, antioxidants, muscle strain, biostimulants of plant and animal origin), which are capable of acting on the body cause an anti-stressor general adaptation reaction. However, the majority authors include only substances capable of causing a condition as adaptogens "non-specifically increased resistance" of the organism to the influence of adverse factors environmental factors of a physical, chemical and biological nature [N.V. Lazarev, 1958; I.I. Brehman, 1957, 1987; I.V. Dardymov, 1976; Saratykov A.S., Krasnov E.A., 1987; Kaplan E.A. and others, 1990; Yakovlev G.M. and others, 1990; I.L. Popovych, 2011; Panossian AG et al, 2022]. They are another form of adaptogenic effect of the means regulatory [Saratikov A.S., Krasnov E.A., 1987] ambivalent-equilibrator [Balanovsky V.P. et al., 1993] effect, that is, normalization abnormal body parameters regardless of their orientation.

One of the long-known and widely used adaptogenic means is ball attendants The theoretical basis of balneotherapy and balneorehabilitation is the concept of sanogenesis Gozhenka A.I. and Gozhenko O.A. [2007]. Their main task is to increase the body's resistance, both general and immune, with the goal prevention of aggravation of aseptic inflammation by infection, metaphylaxis relapses in patients in the phase of remission, deepening and prolongation of the latter, suppression of the latent inflammatory process [Cmiyan I.S., 1967, 1973, 2008; I.L. Popovych et al., 2003; Kostyuk P.K. et al., 2006; Babov K.D. et al., 2009; I.L. Popovych, 2011].

Back in 1993, Korneva E.A. [1993; 2020] introduced the term "a single immune-neuro-endocrine complex that participates in ensuring the stability internal environment of the body". I. L. Popovych, barely changing the term to "neuroendocrine-immune complex" [I.L. Popovich, 2009], initiated large-scale studies of immediate and long-term (course) effects on it the famous Naftusya bioactive water, which is a combination non-antigenic (oil-like substances and products of their microbial transformation, primarily fatty acids) and antigenic (indigenous microflora) irritants and fully meets the recently accepted International Scientific criteria Association for Probiotics and Prebiotics (ISAPP) to refer the product to synbiotics: "a mixture containing living microorganisms and substrates selectively used by host microorganisms that provides benefits for the health of the host" [Swanson KS et al., 2020]. The

results were published in a number of monographs [Dranovsky A.L., Popovych I.L., 2010; I.L. Popovych, 2011; Chebanenko O.I., Popovych I.L., 2011; 2012; 2013; 2015; I.L. Popovych et al., 2014; Kozyavkina O.V. et al., 2015; Sydoruk N.O. et al., 2018; Gozhenko AI et al., 2019; Popovych IL et al., 2020; Gozhenko A.I. and others, 2021; Popovych IL et al., 2022; Korda M.M. et al., 2023] and numerous articles Truskavet Scientific School of Balneology, which aroused great interest in specialists and were recognized by experts as the main trend of the last decade in Ukrainian balneology [A.G. Portnichenko, 2015].

At the same time, in the process of studying the impact of transdermal devices electrostimulation on the human body, it was found that changes in parameters neuroendocrine-immune complex and metabolome also have adaptogenic character [Popovych IL, 2022; Babelyuk VE and Popovych IL, 2023]. So, the mentioned authors of the concept of anti-stress general adaptive reactions were still right about the wide spectrum of the nature of adaptogens.

Connection of work with scientific programs, plans, topics. The research was carried out along the lines of:

programs of the Institute of Physiology named after O.O. Bogomolets National Academy of Sciences of Ukraine "Study of the mechanisms of regulation of the body's functional systems in conditions of normality and pathology" (No. DR 0102U002064), fragments of which are topics Department of Experimental Balneology "Influence of factors of the Truskavets resort on vegetative and vascular tone and heart activity"; "Mechanisms of induction of the body's protective systems by spa attendants of the Truskavets resort"; "Immunological aspects of balneotherapy at the Truskavets resort of diseases organs of the urinary system" (order No. 104/1–142 of the Institute dated February 25, 1998 p);

of the general resort theme of the Association of Scientists of the city "Integral Quantitative assessment of the general state of health (vitality) of various categories of persons who arrive at the Truskavets resort, the impact on it is standard

balneotherapy complex and the search for methods of increasing efficiency of balneotherapy, balneo-rehabilitation and balneosanitation" (No. DR 0104U007397).

The aim of the study. Find out the role of the neuroendocrine-immune complex in the mechanism of therapeutic and prophylactic action of adaptogens of different nature (phyto-balneo-, electrogenic) and to evaluate the contributions of the components of the composition of adaptogens (polyphenols, fatty acids, bacteria) in their influence on parameters neuroendocrine-immune complex.

Research tasks. To achieve the goal, it is necessary solve the following problems.

1. In the clinical and physiological observations, register short-term (within 1.5 hours) reactions of the parameters of the neuroendocrine-immune complex on the use of Naftusya bioactive water and phytoadaptogen and related changes parameters of gastric and pancreatic secretion, cholekinetics, urination and hemodynamics. Identify predictors of options for short-term reactions on adaptogens.
2. Investigate changes in the parameters of the neuroendocrine-immune complex under by the influence of the course of drinking Naftusya bioactive water, the use of phytoadaptogens or transcutaneous electrical stimulation of nerve plexuses by the author device "VEB". To find out which changes in parameters of the neuroendocrine immune complex are the same for adaptogens of different nature (common), and which specific
3. Based on specific effects, evaluate the contributions of individual components adaptogens (aryl hydrocarbons, fatty acids and bacteria) in their effects on neuro-endocrine-immune complex. 4. To analyze the correlation relationships between the parameters of the central and autonomous nervous, endocrine and immune systems as components neuroendocrine-immune complex. Find out the relationship between the parameters neuroendocrine-immune complex and their changes, as factors signs, and microbiota of urine and feces, metabolism of lipids, electrolytes and nitrogenous metabolites, hemodynamics, cholekinetics, gastric and pancreatic secretion, acupuncture and gas discharge visualization - as effective signs
5. In experiments on rats, conduct a comparative study of preventive effects of phytoadaptogen and Naftusya bioactive water on changes in the neuroendocrine immune complex, metabolome and markers of myocardial damage and gastric mucosa under the influence of acute immobilization-cold factors stress Analyze neuroendocrine-immune interrelationships and find out the role of the neuroendocrine-immune complex in minimizing stressors damage to the myocardium and gastric mucosa.
6. Identify options for reactions of the neuroendocrine-immune complex of rats to chronic immobilization stress and analyze neuroendocrine immune relationships.

7. Identify general and specific changes in neuroendocrine-immune parameters complex of animals with their course load of fresh and mineral waters of different chemical composition. Analyze the connections between the content of tested waters of organic substances, microelements and electrolytes, with on the one hand, and the parameters of the neuroendocrine-immune system exposed to them of the complex - on the other hand.

8. Assess the contributions of autochthonous microflora and bioactive organic substances of Naftusya water in its effects on neuroendocrine-immune parameters of the

complex The object of research is the neuroendocrine-immune complex, microbiota, metabolome, hemodynamics, cholekinetics, gastric and pancreatic secretion, biophysical parameters. Subject of

research in humans:

Amplitude-frequency and spectral parameters of the electroencephalogram: average amplitude (μV), average frequency (Hz), frequency deviation (Hz), index rhythm (%), asymmetry coefficient (%), lateralization coefficient (%), absolute ($\mu V^2 / Hz$) and relative (%) spectral power density (SPD) of the main rhythms: δ (35÷13 Hz), θ (13÷8 Hz), α (8÷4 Hz) and β (4÷0.5 Hz) in 16 loci (Fp1, Fp2, F3, F4, F7, F8, C3, C4, T3, T4, P3, P4, T5, T6, O1, O2). Entropy is relative SHSP in these loci.

Temporal and spectral parameters of heart rate variability (HRV): HR, Mo, AMo, MxDMn, TNN, SDNN, RMSSD, pNN50, absolute (msec²) and relative (%) spectral power of HRV components: HF (0.4÷0.15 Hz), LF (0.15÷0.04 Hz), VLF (0.04÷0.015 Hz), ULF (0.015÷0.003 Hz) and their entropy. Adaptation hormones:

cortisol, aldosterone, triiodothyronine, testosterone, calcitonin

Hormones of the gastroentero-pancreatic neuroendocrine system (GEPES): gastrin, glucagon, insulin.

Parameters of immune status: leukocytes and leukocytogram; relative the content in the blood of lymphocytes that express CD3, CD4, CD8, CD22, CD25 and CD56 receptors and T-lymphocytes with a high affinity for CD2 receptors, as well as sensitive and resistant to theophylline; serum content of immunoglobulins G, A, M, circulating immune complexes, C-RP, IL-1, IL-6, TNF- γ ; activity, intensity and completeness of phagocytosis by neutrophils of blood cultures

Staphylococcus aureus (ATCC N 25423 F49) and Escherichia coli (O55 K59); entropy leukocytograms and immunocytograms; author's leukocyte indices of adaptation and tension; content of lysozyme, sIgA, IgA, IgG in saliva.

Fecal microbiota: normal, hemolyzing and weakened E. coli enzymatic activity, Klebsiella, Proteus, Bifidobacteria, Lactobacilli. Bacteriuria, leukocyturia and erythrocyturia. Parameters of the metabolome: the

content of triglycerides and cholesterol in the plasma composition of lipoproteins of high, low and very low density, in plasma and urine -

creatinine, urea, uric acid, phosphates, chloride, sodium, potassium, calcium and magnesium. Hemodynamic

parameters: EDV, ESV, SV, ET, HR, BPs, BPd, GPRV, the author's index of the contractile activity of the heart.

Cholekinetics parameters: gallbladder volumes on an empty stomach and after 5-60 min after standard cholekinetics and/or Naftusya water.

Parameters of gastric secretion: intragastric pH-metry and/or gastric probing on an empty stomach and after the introduction of Naftusya water with determination of the titrated acid and pepsin.

Parameters of pancreatic secretion: duodenal probing on an empty stomach and after introduction of Naftusya water with determination of bicarbonate, amylase, lipase and trypsin.

Biophysical parameters: electrical conductivity of acupuncture points, area, shape, entropy and symmetry of the gas discharge image, energy and asymmetry virtual chakras.

Subject of research in rats

ECG and variation cardiointervalogram parameters (Mo, AMo and MxDMn). The mass of the adrenal glands and the thickness of their glomerular, fascicular, reticular and medullary zones. Plasma levels of adaptation hormones (corticosterone, triiodothyronine and testosterone). Excretion with daily urine 17-ketosteroids.

The concentration of electrolytes in the blood (Na^+ , K^+ , Mg^{2+} , Ca^{2+} , Cl^- , phosphates), nitrogenous metabolites (creatinine, urea, uric acid, bilirubin), medium molecular weight polypeptides, glucose, amylase, cholesterol alpha- and non-alpha-lipoproteins, products of lipoperoxidation (diene conjugates and malondialdehyde), activity of antioxidant protection enzymes (superoxide dismutase of erythrocytes and catalase of erythrocytes and plasma) and cytolysis (AIT, AsT, acid and alkaline phosphatase, creatine phosphokinase). Majority the listed indicators of metabolism were also determined in daily urine.

Hormonal activities: parathyroid - according to coefficients (Sar/Pr) 0.5 , (Pu/Cau) 0.5 and (Cap•Pu/Pp•Cau) 0.25, calcitonin - according to coefficients (1/ÿÿÿ•ÿÿ) 0.5 , (Cau•Pu) 0.5 and (Cau•Pu/Cap•Pp) 0.25 and mineralocorticoid - by coefficients (Nap/Kp) 0.5 , (Ku/Nau) 0.5 and (Nap•Ku/Kp•Nau) 0.25.

The mass of the thymus and the relative content of T-lymphocytes, lymphoblasts, epitheliocytes, endotheliocytes, reticulocytes, macrophages and corpuscles in the thymocytogram Gassal. The mass of the spleen and the relative content of lymphocytes, lymphoblasts, plasma cells, reticulocytes, fibroblasts, macrophages, microphages and eosinophils in the splenocytogram. Peripheral blood leukocytes and their relative content leukocytograms of basophils, eosinophils, rod- and segmentonuclear cells neutrophils, monocytes and lymphocytes. Relative content in the immunocytogram theophylline-resistant theophylline-sensitive T-lymphocytes, granule-containing large lymphocytes, B-lymphocytes, plasma cells and 0-lymphocytes. Entropy of thymocytogram, splenocytogram, leukocytogram and immunocytogram.

Reaction of blast transformation of T-lymphocytes to phytohemagglutinin. Indexes phagocytic function of neutrophils (microphages) and monocytes (macrophages): phagocytic index, microbial number, killing index and bactericidal ability against *Staphylococcus aureus* (ATCC strain N25423 F49). Microbiota

feces. Subject of research in dogs

HEPES hormones gastrin, glucagon, insulin.

Research methods: electrophysiological - for recording indicators the functional state of the central and autonomic nervous systems; radioimmuno - for determination of gastrin, glucagon and insulin; immunoenzymatic - for determination of adaptation hormones, cytokines and immunoglobulins; immune - for determination of immunity indicators; morphological - to study the condition adrenal glands, thymus and spleen; biochemical - to determine indicators metabolome; microbiological - to assess the microbiota of feces and urine; ultrasound - to determine hemodynamic indicators; biophysical - for determination of electrical conductivity of acupuncture points and gas discharge parameters visualization; statistical - for mathematical analysis of digital material.

Experimental studies were conducted according to the rules and requirements of the "General principles of working with animals", approved by I National Congress on Bioethics (Kyiv, 2001), agreed with provisions of the "European Convention on the Protection of Vertebrate Animals, which are used for experimental and other scientific purposes" (Council of Europe, No. 123, Strasbourg, 1985) and the Law of Ukraine "On the Protection of Animals from cruel treatment" dated 26.02.2006. Removal of animals from the experiment was carried out under light inhalation (ether) anesthesia by decapitation.

Tests in patients were performed in accordance with the provisions of Helsinki declaration of 1975, revised and supplemented in 2002, and the directive of the National Committee on the Ethics of Scientific Research. During the event Informed consent was obtained from all participants of the tests and all were used measures to ensure anonymity of participants.

Research protocols were approved by the Ethics Committees of the Institute of Physiology named after O.O. Bogomolets National Academy of Sciences and State University "Ukrainian Research Institute of transport medicine" of the

Ministry of Health. Scientific novelty of the obtained results

Ambiguous and contradictory data about correlations between electroencephalogram (EEG) parameters and heart rate variability (HRV), which reflects functional relationships between the central and autonomic nervous systems.

The concept of the immunological homunculus is filled with new facts. In particular, the EEG loci on which nerve structures responsible for the regulation of phagocytosis of gram-positive and gram-negative cells are projected bacteria Information on EEG loci previously known to be responsible for others

immune processes, complemented by data on the type of rhythms generated by neural structures that project to these loci, as well as on the inhibitory or activating nature of regulation. The concept of the

neuroendocrine-immune complex gained further development through a quantitative and qualitative integral assessment of the relationships between the parameters of the nervous, endocrine and immune systems declared by previous authors. On this basis, the concept of general adaptive reactions of the organism (GASS) was significantly supplemented and specified. In particular, the author's leukocyte indices of adaptation and tension are proposed for the quantitative assessment of qualitatively different ZARO of stress and overactivation, as well as disharmonious and harmonious reactions to training, calm and increased activation. The existing classical criteria of leukocytogram and levels of glucocorticoid, mineralocorticoid, thyroid and sex hormones in the blood for the identification of the type of ZARO are supplemented with calcitonin and parameters of VRS, EEG and immunity. The listed hormones together with the VRS-marker of sympathetic tone (LFnu) are included in the author's six-member neuro-endocrine stress index, which is a significantly supplemented and modified version of the stress factor of V.V. Frolkis. [1990]. Physiological correlates of known information parameters: harmony,

synchronization and entropy were discovered for the first time, and they were used for the integral assessment of the state of the human and rat organism and the impact of pathogenic and sanogenic factors on it.

For the first time, it was found that the inhibitory or activating nature of the vagal influence on the blood level of pro-inflammatory cytokines is determined by the constellation of the initial parameters of the EEG, HRS, immunity and metabolome and can be accurately predicted with the help of classification functions obtained as a result of discriminant analysis. This resolves the controversy existing in the literature regarding the concept of the cholinergic anti-inflammatory reflex.

In experiments with simulation of acute and chronic stress, variants of immune responses were found, which are accompanied by characteristic changes in the parameters of the autonomic nervous and endocrine systems and the metabolome.

In experiments on rats, it was shown for the first time that preventive weekly use of Naftusia bioactive water (BAVN), in general, similar to the reference adaptogen ginseng, limits, nullifies, reverses neuro-hormonal, metabolic and immune pathogenic manifestations of acute immobilization-cold stress and enhances its sanogenic manifestations, without significantly influencing indicators that are not subject to stressor action. This is accompanied by the minimization of metabolic and ECG markers of dystrophic and necrotic damage to the myocardium and erosive-ulcerative damage to the gastric mucosa. The stress-mitigating effect of BAVN is reproduced by organic substances extracted from it. The patent "Method of prevention of erosive and ulcerative lesions of the gastric mucosa in laboratory animals" was obtained.

In a comparative experiment, the similarity of stress limiters was revealed effects of the domestic phytocomposition "Balsam of the Crimea" with such ginseng and BAVN, which gave reason to patent it as an adaptogenic agent.

By using natural potable medicinal waters and their artificial ones of salt analogues in the experiment, a quantitative assessment was carried out and the role of their effects on the neuroendocrine-immune complex and the metabolism of electrolytes, trace elements and organic substances. For the first time, it has been proven that it is organic nitrogen and carbon have the maximum modulating effect on the neuroendocrine-immune complex, trace elements are less effective, while the effect of electrolytes minimal despite their mass superiority.

Through three-month monitoring of Naftusya water of various wells It was shown for the first time that fluctuations in the chemical composition of the Truskavet deposit water is accompanied by fluctuations in its biological and physiological activity, between which there is a significant canonical correlation. By weekly watering of rats with tap water, bottled water "Truskavetska", which contains petroleum-like organic

substances, but devoid of hydrocarbon-oxidizing bacteria and produced them of fatty acids, and Naftusya water with subsequent modeling of acute the individual contributions of immobilization-cold stress were assessed for the first time aryl hydrocarbons and bacteria/fatty acid complex in stress-limiting effects Naftusya waters.

In an experiment using tap water, Naftusya water and culture fluid filtered from microbes, which contains products biotransformation of hydrocarbons of the water-bearing rock of the Truskavet deposit culture of hydrocarbon-oxidizing bacteria previously isolated from Naftusi, polyvariance of own effects of organic substances (OR) was revealed and microbes Naftusi. In particular, both factors are comparable stimulants effects on the mass of the thymus, the content of plasma cells in the spleen, in the blood - B- and theophylline-sensitive T-lymphocytes, as well as phagocytosis by neutrophils/microphages Staph. aureus. Levels in the blood of leukocytes in general and eosinophils in particular and lymphoblasts in the spleen grow under the influence of OR only, and at theophylline-resistant T-lymphocytes in the blood and reticulocytes in the thymus, as well as the thickness of the fascicular layer of the cortex of the adrenal glands is made stimulating, and bacteria - inhibitory effect. Instead, ORs reduce the thickness of the reticular layer of the adrenal cortex, suppress phagocytosis by monocytes/macrophages Staph. aureus, reduce the content of plasma cells in the thymus, as well as ordinary E. coli and its strain with hemolytic ability in feces, while these parameters are not subordinate under the influence of Naftusi bacteria. Instead, Naftusi bacteria cause a significant increasing the content of Bifidobacteria and Lactobacilli probiotics in feces, as well as lymphocytes in the thymus, while the effect of OR on these parameters is opposite. Finally, the content of macrophages in the thymus under the influence of Naftusi bacteria decreases, while OR ineffective.

By giving rats tap water, native Naftusei, that is, with living microflora, as well as Naftusei, in which the microflora was killed by ultraviolet radiation or removed by filtration through special sieve, the quantitative contributions of organic substances, living substances were found out for the first time microbes and their antigens in antixenobiotic, endocrine, immunotropic and metabolic effects of this healing water. Joint

reactions of the neuroendocrine-immune complex were revealed for the first time rats on course drinking BAVN or applications of ozokerite, which are caused, presumably, by the influence of their oil-like organic substances, primarily aromatic, on aryl hydrocarbon receptors (aryl hydrocarbon receptor AhR) terminals of afferent fibers of sensory neurons and/or macrophages gut-associated lymphoid tissue (GALT) or skin (SALT) in accordance.

It was demonstrated for the first time in clinical and physiological observations an opportunity to increase the effectiveness of the balneotherapy complex Truskavets resort (drinking BAVN, ozokerite applications, mineral baths) by additionally including phytoadaptogens in its composition.

For the first time, it was found that a number of neuroendocrine-immune parameters of the complex and RHV changes in the same way under the influence of the course of both the use of BAVN and transcutaneous electrical stimulation of nerve plexuses with the "VEB" device. It additionally indicates the involvement of the nervous system in the mechanism of action of BAVN.

In a comparative clinical and physiological study with a weekly using BAVN (as a complex of at least polyphenols, fatty acids and autochthonous bacteria), domestic phytocomposition "Balsam Truskavets" (as a complex of at least polyphenols and fatty acids) and ozokerite extract (as sources of polyphenols/aryl hydrocarbons) constellations were discovered for the first time parameters of the neuroendocrine-immune complex, which change in the same way extent, on the other hand, the reactions of other constellations of parameters are divergent. The obtained data allowed quantitative mathematical modeling to assess the individual contributions of polyphenols, fatty acids and autochthonous microflora BAVN in its effects on the neuro-endocrine-immune complex, presumably mediated by Ah, GP40/120 and TL/NL receptors, respectively. This is documented complete compliance of native Naftusa with the criteria of synbiotics.

On the basis of the obtained results, a theory of the curative and preventive action of the balneotherapy agents of the Truskavets resort was created, xenobiotic-synbiotic based on active principles and neuroendocrine-immune adaptogenic

according to the mechanism of their implementation and essence.

At least three effectors of adaptogens: polyphenols, fatty acids and bacteria (together they are a synbiotic) through the corresponding receptors (Ah, GP40/120, TL/NL) affect neurons of the enteric nervous system (ENS) and immunocytes GALT/SALT, as well as on microbiota cells. Released under this influence neurotransmitters and cytokines, in turn, act autocrine and paracrine

effects on the same or neighboring neurons and immunocytes, as well as on neurons of the autonomic and central nervous systems, reaching them through the blood and irritating afferent terminals n. vagus and n. splanchnicus (as well as the skin during application or cupping). Next, the corresponding cortical and subcortical nerve structures have a modulating effect on the immunocytes of the bone marrow, thymus, spleen, lymph nodes, and again GALT/SALT (as well as BALT, MALT, etc.), and on endocrinocytes, at least in the cortex of the adrenal glands, gonads, and thyroid gland, hormones which, in turn, affect immunocytes. A direct effect of absorbed polyphenols and fatty acids on endocrinocytes and blood/lymph immunocytes is also possible. Cells of the microbiota under the influence of polyphenols and/or other organic substances that act as prebiotics begin to multiply, as a result of which the production and release of fatty acids and endogenous AhR agonists increases, which potentiates the effects of both exogenous agonists on neurons, immunocytes and endocrinocytes. Another consequence of the activation of the proliferation of microbiota is the strengthening of its immunomodulatory effect, as well as its antimicrobial effect against pathogenic microflora and strengthening the barrier against the latter. The result of the action of adaptogens is the normalization or minimization of disorders (or even optimization) of the neuro-endocrine-immune complex, and the final result is the suppression or resolution of chronic inflammation of the digestive and genitourinary (probably also respiratory, through BALT) systems with improvement or normalization of their functional state.

Approbation of the results. The results were made public at the following gatherings: IX All-Union Congress of Physiotherapists and Spa Specialists (Tashkent, 1989); XIII Congress of the Ukrainian Physiological University named after I.P. Pavlova (Kharkiv, 1990); IV All-Union Congress of Gastroenterologists (Leningrad, 1990); V congress of physiotherapists and spa specialists of Ukraine (Odesa, 1991); XIV Congress of the Ukrainian Physiological Society named after I.P. Pavlova (Kyiv, 1994); I Russian congress on pathophysiology (Moscow, 1996); VII Ukrainian Biochemical Congress (Kyiv, 1997); XV Congress of the Ukrainian Physiological University named after I.P. Pavlova (Donetsk, 1998); 1st National Congress of Physiotherapists and Resort Specialists of Ukraine (Khmilnyk, 1998); VII Congress of the World Federation of Ukrainian Medical Societies (Uzhhorod, August 1998); III National Congress of Pathophysiologists of Ukraine (Odesa, 2000); VIII Congress of the World Federation of Ukrainian Medical Societies (Lviv, Truskavets, 2000); III national congress of physiotherapists and spa specialists (Yalta, 2006); III All-Russian conference "Fundamental aspects of compensatory and adaptive processes" (Novosibirsk, 2007); 5th National Congress of Pathophysiologists of Ukraine (Zaporizhia, 2008); III congress of physiotherapists, spa specialists and medical rehabilitators (Yalta, 2008); scientific and practical conferences "Actual issues of pathology under conditions of action of extraordinary factors on the body" (Ternopil, 2008; 2009; 2010; 2012; 2013; 2015; 2017; 2018; 2020); international symposium "Actual problems of biophysical medicine" (Kyiv, 2009; 2012; 2014; 2016); reading them V.V. Podvysotskyi

(Odesa, 2009; 2010; 2012; 2015; 2017; 2018); III Congress of Physiologists of the CIS (Yalta, 2011); VI National Congress of Pathophysiologists of Ukraine (Yalta, 2012); X Anniversary Ukrainian-Polish-Belorussian Conference "Physiology and Pathology of Respiration: Advances in Basic Research and Clinical Application (Kyiv, 2013); Konferencje Naukowe "Jakość w Sporcie" (Toruń, Poland, 2013); XIX Congress Ukrainian Physiological University named after P.G. Kostyuka (Lviv, 2014); VII National Congress of Pathophysiologists of Ukraine (Kharkiv, 2016); XVI International Conference "The current status and approaches to development of physical and rehabilitation medicine in Ukraine according to international standards" (Kyiv, 2016); 11th international conference "Acent Graphics Communications and Publishing" (Hamilton, Canada, 2019); The 20th Congress of the Ukrainian Physiological University named after P.G. Kostyuka (Kyiv, 2019); Galician readings (Ivano-Frankivsk, 2019); 19th International Applied Research Conference (Kyiv, 2019); VIII National congress of pathophysiologists of Ukraine (Odesa, 2020); Galician readings II (Ternopil, 2020); National Congress of Physical and Rehabilitation Medicine&Balneology (Covasna, 2021, Romania); Ukrainian conference on Neuroscience dedicated to the 90th birthday of academician Vladimir Skok (Kyiv, 2022); All-Ukrainian Science and Technology conf. "Prospects for the development of medical and physical rehabilitation in different levels of medical care" (Ternopil, 2022). Publications. Research

results are reflected in 29 articles published in journals of Ukraine, Poland, Romania, Italy, Iran and the USSR, which indexed in the scientometric database Scopus, and 116 articles in professional journals of Ukraine, Poland, Romania and the USSR, as well as in 32 monographs, including individual, recommended for publication by the Academic Councils of the Institute of Physiology named after O.O. Bogomolets National Academy of Sciences and UkrNDI of Medicine, Transport, Ministry of Health. Received 2 patents

Hirsch indexes: Scopus 4 (35 citations), Research Gate 13 (623 citations), Google Scholar 35 (3592 citations). Research Interest Score 234.4.

RESEARCH RESULTS AND THEIR DISCUSSION

At the preliminary stage, it was found that a single use of Naftusya bioactive water (BAVN) causes a reaction of the gastroentero-pancreatic neuroendocrine system (GEPES), in particular its key representative gastrin, after only 2 minutes (in dogs, Fig. 1), and GEPES and the autonomic nervous system systems in humans (Fig. 2-4) - no later than after 15-20 minutes (first registration), which is observed for at least 1.5 hours.

Fig. 1. Dynamics of the gastrinemic response to BAVN in dogs with low (GL) and high (GH) basal gastrin levels

4 variants of the urgent reaction of the autonomic nervous system (according to individual changes in the classic Baevsky stress index) to BAVN were identified: early (*r/s* 20 min) sympathicotonic (in 49%), late (*r/s* 40 min) vagotonic (in 32%), early vagotonic (in 10.5%), late sympathicotonic (in 8.5%).

Fig. 2. Variants of the emergency response of the autonomic nervous system to BAVN: early (E) and late (T), sympathicotonic (S) and vagotonic (V)

Such variants of vegetative reactions to BAVN are accompanied by characteristic changes in the content of gastrin (Fig. 3) and glucagon (Fig. 4) in the blood, the pH of the gastric mucosa (Fig. 5) and cholekinetics (Fig. 6), as well as the contractile activity of the myocardium (Fig. 7). This allows us to retrospectively explain the diversity of acute reactions of the digestive and cardiovascular systems during the time interval between the use of BAVN and food, previously discovered by us and other authors.

Fig. 3. Concomitant changes in gastrinemia in various variants of the vegetotropic reaction to BAVN

Fig. 4. Concomitant changes in glucagonemia in various variants of the vegetotropic reaction to BAVN

Fig. 5. Concomitant changes in pH of the gastric mucosa of patients with normal and moderate reduced acidity for various variants of the vegetotropic reaction to BAVN

Fig. 6. Concomitant changes in the volume of the gall bladder under different variants of the vegetotropic reaction to BAVN

Fig. 7. Correlation between the changes 30 minutes after the use of BAVN in the Baevsky stress index (X axis) and the Ruzhilo-Popovich myocardial contractile activity index (Y axis)

The postprandial reaction of the stress index is determined by 54% by the initial levels of autonomic reactivity, diastolic pressure, glucagon and insulin (Fig. 8).

It has been found that the variants of the vegetative response are conditioned by the initial levels, first of all, of insulin, gastrin, and glucagon, as well as vegetative reactivity, fashion, rhythm frequency, diastolic and systolic blood pressure, and even sex. The listed predictors with the help of classifying discriminant functions make it possible to predict the reaction options with an accuracy of 83%.

Abstract

2

$R = 0.736; R^2 = 0.542$
 $(12) = 97.2; p < 0.0002; y Prime = 0.412$

Fig. 8. Canonical correlation between the initial VRS parameters (X axis) and changes 20, 40, and 60 min after

use of the BAVN stress index of Baskin et al. (1997) in the subsequent analysis of the data. We found that a constellation of 4 temporal and spatial parameters determines the severity of the vascular

2

$R = 0.927; R^2 = 0.860; y$
 $(15) = 46; p < 10^{-4}; y Prime = 0.143$

Fig. 9. Canonical correlation between the initial EEG and VRS parameters (X axis) and changes after 1 hour after using BAVN Baskin stress index (Y axis)

Each variant of the vegetative reaction to BAVN is preceded by a corresponding one the constellation of 19 EEG spectral parameters that conditions it unmistakably (Fig. 10). In particular, the late sympathotonic reaction is determined minimum values of spectral power density for sampling (ShSP) of the delta rhythm in the Fp1 locus and theta rhythm in the F7, F8 and F4 loci in combination with the maximum for the sample value of the alpha-rhythm SHSP in the T4 locus, information about which is condensed in the first root. At the opposite pole the root axes are localized points of patients with an early sympathotonic reaction, which is determined by the maximum/minimum values of SHSP in these loci. Intermediate values of EEG predictors condition vagotonic reactions. At

it turned out to be additional predictors of late vagotonic reaction the maximum for the sample of values of SHSP beta rhythm in loci F7, F8 and T6 and of the theta rhythm in the Fp2 and P3 loci in combination with the minimal SSHSP of the delta rhythm in information about which is condensed in the second root.

Fig. 10. Individual values of the first two roots of EEG predictors of response options of the autonomic nervous system at BAVN

A very strong canonical correlation was found between changes in the stress index, with on the one hand, and 16 EEG parameters on the other hand (Fig. 11).

The ranking of partial correlation coefficients has the following form: variability of the δ -rhythm ($r=0.71$), SHSP F3- δ ($r=0.44$), T3- δ ($r=0.42$), P3- δ ($r=0.32$), lateralization of the δ -rhythm ($r=0.26$), SHSP F4- δ ($r=0.27$), O2- δ ($r=0.27$), δ -rhythm index ($r=0.26$), δ -rhythm asymmetry ($r=0.26$), SHSP T4- δ ($r=0.26$), C4- δ ($r=0.26$), T3- δ ($r=0.25$), C3- δ ($r=-0.36$), C4- δ ($r=-0.31$), T3- δ ($r=-0.28$), Fp1- δ ($r=-0.25$).

Change

R=0.952; R2=0.906; $\bar{y}$ Fig. 11. Canonical (16)=71; $\bar{y}$ Prime=0.094; $p < 10^{-6}$

-6

correlation between changes 1 hour after the use of BAVN Baevsky stress index (X axis) and 16 EEG parameters (Y axis)

However, in another observation, it was found that urgent (registered after 1.5 hours, when patients usually eat) polyvariant vegetotropic (sympathotonic - in 50%, vagotonic - in 39%, neutral - in 11%) reactions to BAVN (n=19) are non-specific, that is, they do not differ from those for fresh water (n=15) or for the phytopreparation "Balsam of the Crimea" (n=20) (identified and patented by us earlier as an adaptogen), but again they are conditioned with absolute accuracy by the initial level of VRS -markers of sympathetic (AMO) and vagal (triangular index) tone and constellation of 21 EEG parameters, 8 immunity parameters, as well as personal anxiety. Non-specific reactions of the central nervous system are manifested in the form of an increase in the delta-rhythm SHSP in the Fp1 and F7 loci and theta-rhythm in the T5, O2, F8 and F7 loci (in descending order) in combination with a decrease in the theta-rhythm SHSP in the C3 locus. A discriminant analysis was conducted in order to identify exactly those parameters, according to the set of postprandial reactions of which the control and adaptogenic groups differ significantly. The forward stepwise program includes 13 parameters in the discriminant model (Table 1). Another result of the discriminant analysis is the possibility to visualize the postprandial reaction of each patient by calculating the individual values of the canonical discriminant root as the sum of the products of unstandardized coefficients by the individual values of the discriminant variables plus a constant (Table 1 and Fig. 12). It was found that the specificity of the acute reactions to both adaptogens (BAVN and balsam) nevertheless takes place and is manifested in the leveling or reversion of the theta rhythm in the P3 locus and the frequency of the delta rhythm, which were reduced in the water control of SHSP, on the one hand, and the reduction, leveling or reversions of elevated

water control of the alpha-rhythm in the F7, P3, C3 and T3 loci, beta-rhythm in on the O1 and O2 loci and the delta rhythm in the P3 locus - on the other hand. In addition, adaptogens cause a tendency to further decrease relative power of the VLF component of the VRS, while in the water control this parameter increases somewhat. The neurotropic effects of adaptogens are accompanied by an increase relative to water control of the intensity of phagocytosis by Staph neutrophils. aureus and the blood level of T-helpers in combination with a decrease in the level of B-lymphocytes.

Table 1. Structural and unstandardized coefficients for EEG, VRS, and immunity parameters, whose reactions to adaptogens and water control differ significantly

Variables currently in the model	Coefficients	
	Structural	Raw
PSD P3- δ , δ V2 /Hz	-.315	-.0037
PSD C3- δ , %	-.274	-.1228
PSD F7- δ , %	-.249	-.0341
PSD T3- δ , %	-.242	.0608
PSD VLF band HRV, %	-.227	-.0357
PSD P3- δ , δ V2 /Hz	-.216	-.0086
PSD O2- δ , δ V2 /Hz	-.155	-.0081
CD19 ⁺ B-Lymphocytes, %	-.136	-.0536
PSD O1- δ , δ V2 /Hz	-.118	.0129
PSD P3- δ , %	.189	.1615
Microbial Count vs St. aur, V/Ph, 172, 1974		
Theophylline resistant T-Lym, %	.151	.0496
δ -rhythm Frequency, Hz	.126	1.068
	Constant, .0924	
r*=0.743; Wilk's λ =0.447; $\chi^2(13)=37$; p=0.0005		
Squared Mahalanobis Distance=6.16; F=3.73; p=0.0007		

Fig. 12. Individual values of changes in the canonical discriminant root after 1.5 hours after using ordinary water (W), phytoadaptogen (B) and Naftusya bioactive water (N)

Fig. 13. Average ($M \pm SE$) values of changes in the canonical discriminant root after 1.5 h after drinking fresh water, phytoadaptogen and Naftusya bioactive water (BAWN)

So, during the 1.5-hour typical for drinking balneotherapy the interval between the consumption of Naftusya bioactive water and food, a reaction develops 10 parameters of the nervous and 3 parameters of the immune system, significantly different from water control and similar to the reaction to phytoadaptogen (Fig. 13). It gives grounds for nominating Naftusya bioactive water as an adaptogen. However, between the neurotropic effects of BAVN and phytoadaptogen differences were found according to another constellation of parameters, that is, their adaptogenic ones properties are not identical. Now let's

consider how a 7-10-day course of balneotherapy at the resort had an effect Truskavets for 44 patients (including 10 women) with chronic pyelonephritis in phase remission. It is known that BAVN is extremely used as a monotherapy factor rarely, usually drinking water three times a day is combined with mineral baths and applications of ozokerite every other day. In our observation, monotherapy received 23 patients, BAVN and fountains - 8, BAVN and ozokerite - 3, BAVN, ozokerite and fountains - 10 patients. Screening of individual reactions to balneotherapy revealed 10 patterns: 6 stimulating (upregulating) and 4 inhibitory (downregulating). The first

stimulating pattern (Fig. 14) combines 11 parameters, levels which at admission were significantly reduced, and under the influence of balneotherapy grew significantly, but still remained low. In particular, it is the entropy of VRS, the index of killing by neutrophils *E. coli* and *Staph. aureus*, the relative content of T-helpers in the blood, Bifidobacteria and Lactobacilli in the feces and the gross content of *E. coli*, the concentration of phosphates in the urine, daily excretion of creatinine, author's leukocyte adaptation index, as well as calcitoninemia (only in men). The second pattern reflects the complete normalization of moderately reduced levels bactericidal ability of neutrophils in relation to both types of microbes, natriemia and

phosphaturia, as well as the contractile reaction of the gallbladder to standard cholekinetics. The third pattern reflects a slight, but statistically significant increase within the normal range of calcitoninemia in women, the frequency of beta and alpha rhythms, the SRS of the alpha rhythm in the F7 and T6 loci, as well as the delta rhythm in the T3 locus. The fourth pattern combines 5 parameters (cortisolemia, asymmetry of the delta rhythm and SHSP theta rhythm in the F7, T5 and T6 loci), the quasi-zero initial Z-scores of which increase to 0.36-0.54 Z. And similar initial levels of chloridemia and magnesium and calciuria in the following pattern reach the upper normal zone under the influence of balneotherapy. Finally, parameters of the last stimulating pattern (diuresis, excretion of chloride and urea, as well as serum IgG) move from the upper normal zone even higher.

Fig. 14. Profiles of stimulating effects of balneotherapy

The first inhibitory pattern (Fig. 15) reflects the movement of triiodothyronine levels in plasma and the concentrations of uric acid and sodium in urine from the quasi-zero zone to the lower-score normal zone, as well as the transformation of the initially symmetrical alpha rhythm into a left-sided one. On the other hand, in the second pattern of SHSP theta rhythm in the T4 locus, the basal volume of the gallbladder, and creatinine in women drop from the upper normal zone to the quasi-zero level. The third pattern reflects the normalization of moderately elevated levels of plasma testosterone and urea in both sexes, creatininemia in men, as well as leukocyturia and relative fecal content of *E. coli* strains with hemolytic ability. Finally, the fourth pattern reflects a decrease, but without normalization, of the significantly increased initial levels of Baevsky's VRS indices: centralization $[(VLF+LF)/HF]$ and the activity of regulatory systems and the author's stress index of the leukocytogram, which are markers of maladaptation. This is combined with a decrease in the relative content of conditionally pathogenic microbes in feces:

strain of *E. coli* with weakened enzymatic ability, *Klebsiella* and *Proteus* - and bacteriuria

Fig. 15. Profiles of inhibitory effects of balneotherapy

So, ambivalent - both stimulating and inhibitory - effects
 Balneotherapy has, as a rule, an equilibrative - normalizing or
 minimizing - character, that is, they are physiologically favorable. In order to identify from
 among the 55 parameters considered above exactly those, for
 the totality of which the condition of patients before and after balneotherapy is significantly different, that is, characteristic, a
 discriminant analysis was again carried out. Program
 forward stepwise, 31 parameters are included in the discriminant model (Table 2), while the rest were found outside the
 model as carriers of redundant/duplicate
 information

Table 2. Selected parameters of EEG, HRV, hormones, immunity, microbiota and metabolome discriminant analysis as characteristic of the effect of balneotherapy (ranking by structural coefficient)

Variables currently in the model	Coefficients		
	Standardized	Structural	Raw
Bifidobacteria faecis, lg CFU/γL	1.235	-0.189	1,157
Lactobacilli faecis, lg CFU/γL	-1.915	-0.188	-1.465
Phosphateuria, mM/24 h	-0.643	-0.173	-0.044
Diuresis, L/24 h	-0.835	-0.111	-1,199
Bactericidity vs <i>St. aureus</i> , 10 ⁹ Bacteria/L	-0.460	-0.107	-0.019
Killing Index vs <i>E. coli</i> , %	1.719	-0.094	0.135
Creatinineuria, mM/24 h	0.427	-0.088	0.116
Sodium Plasma, mM/L	-0.343	-0.085	-0.040
Immunoglobulins G, g/L	-0.257	-0.083	-0.071
Calcitonin, ng/L	-0.187	-0.079	-0.218
Cortisol, nM/L	-0.229	-0.078	-0.001
HRV Entropy, •10 ³	-0.454	-0.075	-3,788
Magnesiumuria, mM/24 h	0.608	-0.073	0.313

Popovych's Adaptation Index-2 T3-	-0,260	-0.073	-0.627
ÿ PSD, ÿV2 /Hz ÿ-	-0,264	-0.070	-0.001
rhythm Frequency, Hz T6-	-0,534	-0.061	-0.696
ÿ PSD, ÿV2 /Hz T6-	-1,320	-0.061	-0.012
ÿ PSD, ÿV2 /Hz ÿ-	-0,172	-0.058	-0.004
rhythm Asymmetry, % T5-ÿ	-0,526	-0.055	-0.023
PSD, % T5-ÿ	-0,720	-0.054	-0.152
PSD, ÿV2 /Hz ÿ-	0,828	-0.044	0.018
rhythm Frequency, Hz E.	-0,950	-0.020	-0.228
coli attenuated faecis, %	1.133	0.147	0.042
Testosterone, nM/L	0,528	0.139	0.336
Sodium Urine, mM/L	0,590	0.130	0.021
Gallbladder Basal Volume, mL	0,252	0.115	0.017
Creatinine Plasma, ÿM/L ÿ-	1,078	0.113	0.083
rhythm Laterality, % Uric	0,744	0.111	0.028
Acid Urine, mM/L Urea	0,744	0.093	0.637
Plasma, mM/L	0,731	0.070	-0.715
(VLF+LF)/HF as Centralization Index	-0	0.047	-0.040
Eigenvalue	p<10	Constant	15.38
Canonical R=0.897; Wilks' ÿ=0.170; ÿ ² -6			
Squared Mahalanobis Distance=19.1; F(32)=8.8; p<10 ⁻⁶			

Fig. 16 demonstrates balneotherapy-induced reduction of one or the other measure of the canonical discriminant root in all patients without exception, which reflects an increase in 22 parameters that are negatively correlated with the root, and reduction of 9 parameters related to the root positively.

Fig. 16. Individual values of the discriminant root before and after a course of balneotherapy with using only Naftusi water (N), Naftusi and font (NB), Naftusi and ozokerite (NO), complete balneocomplex (NBO)

The visual impression of the absence of significant differences between therapeutic effects of Naftusi per se and in combination with fountains and applications ozokerite is documented by calculating the average values of the root (Fig. 17).

Note that this only applies to options selected by the program for detection of differences between the states of the body before and after balneotherapy as such, regardless of the recruitment of balneochinists, that is, it is about their general (non-specific) action. The specifics of the influence of balneotherapy complexes, however

exists, but is characterized by a different constellation of parameters [Popovych AI, 2018, 2019].

Fig. 17. Mean values ($M \pm SE$) of the discriminant root before and after the course of balneotherapy with the use of only water Naftusya (N), Naftusya and a font (NB), full balneo complex (NBO)

Based on the analysis of the relationships between neuroendocrine parameters, with on the one hand, and parameters of immunity - on the other, two canonical pairs were found roots The

neuroendocrine root of the first pair is directly represented, first of all, by Baevsky's classic VRS indices (factor loadings R in parentheses): the stress index is current (0.64) and normalized by age (0.62) and the activity index regulatory systems (0.59). Next are the EEG parameters: the alpha-rhythm systolic pulse in loci T6 (0.46) and F7 (0.11) and theta rhythm in loci T5 (0.42) and T6 (0.13), respectively which is wedged in the plasma level of triiodothyronine (0.28). Another constellation of parameters gives the root negative loads, that is, it represents it inversely: the entropy of HRV components (-0.38) and plasma cortisol levels (-0.26) and aldosterone (-0.16). The

immune root of the first pair represents, first of all, the author's index tension of the leukocytogram (0.91), as well as, directly, the relative level of blood CD56⁺ natural killers and bactericidal ability of blood neutrophils regarding Staph. aureus (0.09). Negative loads on the root give IgG serum (-0.27), Staphylococcus aureus (-0.26) and E. coli (-0.21) neutrophil killing indices, as well as CD4⁺ T-helpers (-0.18).

As a result, the power is mutual (given the bilateral functional relationships through neurotransmitters, hormones and cytokines and the corresponding receptors) of neuroendocrine-immune determination in this sample is 69.2% (Fig. 18).

Immunity

$R=0.832$; $R^2=0.692$; $\bar{y}$ $\lambda^2(189)=293$; $p<10^{-5}$; $\bar{y}$ Prime=0.017

Fig. 18. Dot plot of canonical correlation between neuro-endocrine parameters (X-axis) and immunity parameters (Y axis). The first pair of roots

The neuroendocrine root of the second pair (Fig. 19) directly represents:

testosterone (0.60), entropy of HRV components (0.40), alpha rhythm frequency (0.24) and its lateralization (0.18) and aldosterone (0.11).

$R=0.746$; $R^2=0.557$; $\bar{y}$ $\lambda^2(160)=209$; $p=0.006$; $\bar{y}$ Prime=0.054

Fig. 19. Dot plot of canonical correlation between neuro-endocrine parameters (X-axis) and immunity parameters (Y axis). The second pair of roots

Inversely, the root is represented by the centralization index of HRV (-0.45), SHSP of the theta rhythm in loci T6 (-0.42), T5 (-0.39) and T4 (-0.28), delta rhythm in the locus

T3 (-0.25) and alpha rhythm at the T6 locus (-0.16), as well as sex-normalized calcitonin (-0.30) and current triiodothyronine (-0.20).

Leukocytes

The immune root contains direct information on Staph killing indices. aureus (0.72) and E. coli (0.36) and bactericidal against the latter (0.19), as well as CD56 killers (0.58). They are represented in reverse in the root factor structure of CD4 T-helpers (-0.77), IgG (-0.31), as well as author's adaptation indices (-0.33) and depression (-0.20). The mutual determination of the roots is weaker, but still sufficient strong - 55.7%. Given the main diagnosis of patients, as the main object of the study, the regulatory influence of the neuroendocrine-immune complex were selected. The key parameters of the urinary syndrome are bacteriuria and leukocyturia. It was found that the immune status determines the severity of the urinary syndrome by 87.2% (Fig. 20).

+ natural

+

Fig. 20. Dot plot of canonical correlation between immune status (X-axis) and urinary syndrome (Y axis)

At the same time, the immune status is very closely related to the state of the microbiota (Fig. 21).

Fig. 21. Dot plot of canonical correlation between immune status (X axis) and stool microbiota (Y axis)

BAC
BAC
BAC

The microbiota, in turn, determines the severity of the urinary syndrome
 0.2%. The cumulative effect of microbiota and immunity on the urinary syndrome is only insignificant
 the influence of immunity itself prevails (Fig. 22).

$R=0.952$; $R^2=0.906$; $\bar{y}^2(30)=302$; $p<10^{-6}$; $\bar{y} \text{ Prime}=0.021$

Fig. 22. Dot plot of canonical correlation between immune status and stool microbiota (axis X) and urinary syndrome (Y axis)

Returning to fig. 16, a priori it could be predicted that individual changes under the influence of balneotherapy parameters of urinary syndrome are ambiguous. The following analysis confirmed this prediction. In particular, in 27.3% of patients moderate bacteriuria and leukocyturia disappeared (cluster code B2/B0), and in 43.2% - significantly decreased (B2/B1). Another 18.2% of people do not have bacteriuria was detected, and there was only moderate leukocyturia, which is in the process of balneotherapy decreased (B0/B0). However, in 11.4% (5) of patients, they are weakly expressed bacteriuria and leukocyturia slightly increased (B1/B2). A variety of dynamics is revealed urinary syndrome and accompanying characteristic changes in parameters of the neuroendocrine-immune complex is visualized in fig. 23. 34 parameters turned out to be characteristic.

Neurogenic: amplitude and beta index
 delta rhythms, variability of delta and theta rhythms, asymmetry of theta and alpha rhythms, frequency and lateralization of the alpha rhythm, as well as ULF spectral power
 components of VRS. Endocrine: testosterone, triiodothyronine, aldosterone, calcitonin and parathyrin activity. Immune: total blood leukocytes, activity and completion of phagocytosis by neutrophils Staph. aureus, bactericidal ability of neutrophils against Staph. aureus and E. coli, IgG and C-reactive protein sera, content in stool of ordinary E. coli and Klebsiella&Proteus. They stand separately information parameters: leukocytogram entropy, leukocyte indices adaptations of L.H. Harkava and the author and the author stress index.

ability (0.2), blood-augmented receptors (0.20) and
receptor systems (0.25). The vegeto-endocrine coefficient
of immunity and microbiota is 82% (Fig. 25).

Change in Immunity and Microbiota

$r = 0.9475$, $R^2 = 0.8977$, $n = 22$, $p < 10^{-6}$, y P -value = 0.007

Dot plot of the canonical correlation between the dynamics of immune status and microbiota

(x-axis) and urinary syndrome (y-axis)

Change in ANS and Hormones

$r = 0.905$, $R^2 = 0.819$, $n = 14$, $p < 10^{-6}$, y P -value = 0.0015

Fig. 25. Dot plot of the canonical correlation between the dynamics of vegetative-endocrine regulation

(x-axis) and immunity and microbiota (y-axis)

Cumulative determining influence on the dynamics of urinary syndrome changes

parameters of the autonomous nervous, endocrine and immune systems, as well as microbiota

reaches 92% (Fig. 26).

Brain Knowledge

R=0.950, y

2

(48)-137; p<10^-6; y Prime=0.0088

Fig. 27. Dot plot of the canonical correlation between the dynamics of vegetative-endocrine regulation, immunity and microbiota (X axis) and urinary syndrome (Y axis)

When analyzing the neurogenic regulation of the urinary syndrome, it was found (Fig. 27).

...ive regulation by changes in the frequency of the alpha rhythm (-0.33) and its SHSP in the loci

(F3 0.26), F3 (0.26) and T4 (-0.26), where the cortical nuclei that activate

...ary nuclei of the vagus, and the right amygdala, respectively. They act even more strongly

...generating beta-rhythm, which are projected to the F3 (-0.31) and Fp1 (-0.44) loci, and the delta rhythm in the Fp1 locus (-0.27). Instead, positive regulation is imposed on

...syndrome of a change in the variability of the delta rhythm (0.42) and theta rhythm SHSP in

(F4 0.26), alpha rhythm in locus P4 (0.27) and delta rhythm in locus T6 (0.24). Another unfavorable factor is entropy in loci F4 (0.42) and Fp1 (0.31). The coefficient of neurogenic determination of urinary syndrome is 71.5%.

R=0.846, R2=0.715, y

2

(40)-67; p=0.004; y Prime=0.117

Fig. 27. Dot plot of the canonical correlation between the dynamics of EEG parameters (X axis) and urinary syndrome (Y axis)

urinary syndrome (Y axis)

The identified diversity of the impact of balneotherapy on the severity of urinary syndrome is accurately predicted by the constellation of 20 predictors. This is, first of all, the initial level of bacteriuria, as well as components of the microbiota - ordinary *Escherichia coli* and with weakened enzymatic capacity and *Klebsiella* & *Proteus*; leukocytosis, leukocytogram entropy, leukocyte stress and adaptation indices, C-RP, IL-1, 4 parameters of phagocytosis and 4 parameters of humoral immunity. A similar error-free forecast can also be achieved by the constellation of 28 vegetative-endocrine parameters. One gets the impression that one or another version of the effect of balneotherapy on the severity of urinary syndrome is conditioned by the initial state of the parameters of the neuroendocrine-immune complex, on the one hand, and is determined by their dynamics caused by balneofactors, on the other hand. A meta-analysis of 51 human studies of relationships between various HRV indicators as markers of vagal activity and plasma cytokines as markers of inflammation, conducted by the authors' group [Williams DWP et al., 2019], gave mixed conclusions. Forest plot for the association between vagal and inflammatory markers shows both negative and positive correlation coefficients as well as no correlation. Therefore, research in this direction remains relevant in view of the existing concept of the cholinergic anti-inflammatory pathway [Tracey KJ et al., 2002-2022].

In the observed sample, we found four variants of changes in markers of vagal activity (RMSSD and ln HF) and the level of IL-1 γ in plasma. In 11 (25.0%) persons, its increase (respectively by 10.2 ± 5.1 ms and 1.02 ± 0.37 ln ms²) is accompanied by a decrease in IL-1 γ by 0.96 ± 0.20 pg/ml, that is, the classical cholinergic anti-inflammatory pathway takes place. On the other hand, in 8 (18.2%) people, the decrease in parasympathetic effects (by 12.4 ± 4.2 ms and 0.72 ± 0.19 ln ms, respectively) is associated with an increase in IL-1 γ by 1.10 ± 0.28 pg/ml. However, in 13 (29.5%) individuals, an increase in both vagus tone (by 10.1 ± 2.9 ms and 0.96 ± 0.16 ln ms, respectively) and IL-1 γ level (by 1.20 ± 0.38 pg/ml). Another 12 (27.3%) people showed a simultaneous decrease in vagal tone (by 7.9 ± 2.1 ms and 0.75 ± 0.16 ln ms, respectively) and IL-1 γ level (by 1.57 ± 0.25 pg/ml). So, in 43.2% of cases, inverse relationships were found between the change in vagal tone and the level of pro-inflammatory cytokines in the plasma, and in 56.8% - direct relationships. Connections are approximated by curves of the second order. In the case of inverse dependence for lnHF $R^2=0.526$, for RMSSD $R^2=0.349$; with direct dependence, R^2 reaches 0.470 and 0.415, respectively. Using the method of discriminant analysis, it was established that the type of vagus-cytokine response to balneotherapy is determined by the constellation of 23 neuroendocrine initial parameters. Their levels, expressed in Z-scores, are visualized in the form of two profiles (Fig. 28).

Fig. 28. Profiles of initial neuroendocrine parameters that determine alternative vagus cytokine responses to balneotherapy

Predictors of the type of vagus-cytokine reaction can be divided into several clusters. The first cluster is formed by cortisol and SHSP of the γ -rhythm in the C3, C4, F4 and Fp2 loci, the initial levels of which are quasi-normal ($-0.09 \pm 0.06 \bar{y}$) under the inverse type, on the other hand, significantly exceed the norm ($+0.79 \pm 0.04 \bar{y}$) for the direct type vagus-cytokine reaction. Levels of γ -rhythm SSCs in the Fp2, Fp1 and O2 loci are in the lower ($-0.24 \pm 0.03 \bar{y}$) and upper ($+0.44 \pm 0.10 \bar{y}$) normal zones in accordance. The third cluster is formed by the γ -rhythm SSC in the Fp1, T4, Fp2, O1, O2, C3, T5 and T3 loci, as well as the absolute and relative SSC of the VLF band of the HRS. These predictors of the inverse type of vagus-cytokine reaction are in the lower zone normal ($-0.41 \pm 0.02 \bar{y}$), while the direct type of reaction is preceded by quasi-normal levels ($+0.16 \pm 0.02 \bar{y}$). The heart rate is a kind of watershed point, followed by the marker of sympathetic tone (LFnu), T3- δ erythrocyte sedimentation rate, triiodothyronine, as well as the leukocyte adaptation index, the Z-scores of which, on the contrary, intersect at $0.52 \pm 0.09 \bar{y}$ higher in individuals with an inverse type of vagus-cytokine response. Classification discriminant functions allow the inverse type to be predicted of the vagus-cytokine reaction with an accuracy of 94.7% (with a single error), and the direct type reactions are predicted without error. So, alternative types of vagus-cytokine responses to adaptogenic balneotherapy are determined by the characteristics of the original states of neuroendocrine regulation and can be reliably predicted.

In the comparative clinical and physiological observation of children who arrived at the Truskavets resort from territories contaminated with radionuclides, it is shown (Table 3 and Fig. 29) that the use of standard balneotherapy of the complex (drinking BAVN, ozokerite applications, mineral baths, exercise therapy) causes minimization or normalization of reduced parameters of neutrophil phagocytosis, leukocytogram entropy, levels of T-helpers and natural killers, as well as of the quantitative parameter of the correction test, without significantly affecting the normal ones levels of other parameters of immunity, triiodothyronine and aldosterone. On the other hand,

increased VRS index of Bayevsky activity of regulatory [vegetative] systems and hypercortisolemia decrease to the upper normal range.

Table 3. Children's parameters, the changes of which are characteristic of the effects of the standard balneotherapy complex and the one supplemented with phytoadaptogens

Variables currently in the model	Correlations Variables - Canonical Roots		Z-scores for Variables			Effect of SBTC	Effect of Adapt				
			Base line (37)	Stand BTC (20)	SBTC +Adapt (17)						
Root 1 (77%)	R1	R2 -1.95	+1.31	+2.70	+3.26	+1.39					
Microbian Count, Bacteria/Phagocyte	0.454	0.021	-1.75	-0.52	+0.07	+1.23	+0.59				
Bactericidity Capacity of Neutroph, 10 ⁹ B/L	0.424	0.366	-1.01	-0.61	+0.41	+0.40	+1.02				
CD4 ⁺ T-Lymphocytes, %		0.198	0.083	-0.80	-0.29	+0.25	+0.51	+0.54			
CD16 ⁺ NK-Lymphocytes, %		0.136	0.036	-0.34	+0.01	+0.29	+0.35	+0.28			
Quantity of Proof Test, % norm		0.253	0.105	-0.23	+0.26	+0.80	+0.49	+0.84			
Circulating Immune Complexes, units		0.205	0.241	+0.05	+0.32	+1.69	+0.27	+1.37			
Neutrophils Level, %		0.068	0.075	-0.20	-0.13	+0.18	+0.07	+0.31			
Leukocytes Level, 10 ⁹ /L		0.084	0.155	+0.29	+0.26	+1.00	-0.03	+0.74			
Quality of Proof Test, -(mistakes/2 min)		0.219	0.030	-1.00	-0.84	-0.39	+0.16	+0.45			
IgM Serum, g/l		-0.118	-0.092	+0.07	-0.11	-0.49	-0.18	-0.38			
Pan-Lymphocytes, %		-0.044	0.072	+0.51	+0.45	+0.24	-0.06	-0.21			
Root 2 (23%)	R1	R2 +0.27	-1.66	+1.36	-1.93	+3.02					
Baevskiy's Activity Regulatory Systems Ind		-0.061	0.238	+2.21	+0.97	2.17	-1.24	+1.20			
Cortisol, nM/L		0.016	0.214	+1.95	+1.04	+1.99	-0.91	+0.95			
Centralization Index HRV		-0.018	0.163	+0.18	-0.76	+0.41	-0.94	+1.17			
Baevskiy's HRV Stress Index, units		+0.22	-0.88	+0.11	-1.10	+0.99					
1/Mo HRV as Circulating Catecholamines, p		-0.016	0.276	-1.41	-2.80	-0.87	-1.39	+1.93			
Entropy of Leukocytogram •1000		-0.067	-0.331	-0.75	-0.30	-1.40	+0.45	-1.10			
SDNN HRV, msec		0.004	-0.181	+0.16	+0.77	-0.15	+0.61	-0.92			
Triiodothyronine, nM/L		-0.15	+0.09	-0.21	+0.24	-0.30					
Aldosterone, pM/l		+0.28	+0.47	+0.09	+0.19	-0.38					
CD8 ⁺ T-Lymphocytes, %		-0.004	-0.017				-0.15	-0.12	-0.18	+0.03	-0.06

Fig. 29. Centroids (M±SD) of discriminant roots of children aged 10-12 years of both sexes in the basal period and after a two-week course of standard or supplemented balneotherapy phytoadaptogens "Balm of the Crimea" (n=10) or ginseng tincture (n=7)

Therefore, standard balneotherapy has a normalizing (ambivalent-equilibrating) effect on maladjustment, which is considered one of the attributes of adaptogens. At the same time, the quality parameter of the proofreading test and the level of circulating catecholamines are further reduced, as are normal HRV indices, centralization and tension. Additional inclusion in balneotherapy of a complex of phytoadaptogens (both standard and domestic, previously verified by our laboratory), potentiates essential or initiates non-essential immunotropic and nootropic effects. That is, modeled independent (per se) effects of phytoadaptogens are unidirectional with the effects of balneoadaptogens and are combined with the latter, which is illustrated by unidirectional and variously expressed displacement clusters along the axis of the first radical. At the same time, independent neuroendocrine and entropic effects of phytoadaptogens are opposite to such balneoadaptogens that is illustrated by the multidirectional displacement along the axis of the second radical. Postprandial clusters relative to basal ones (Fig. 29). This causes the ability of combined balneo-phytotherapy to prevent as an inhibitory effect of standard balneotherapy on sympathetic tone and circulating levels of catecholamines and cortisol, as well as activating - on the vagal tone, as well as to initiate a decrease in aldosterone and triiodothyronine levels and neutropenia leukocytograms.

According to the chemists of our laboratory [Datsko O.O. et al., 2007], organic component of Naftusya water, determined by the method of solid-phase extraction in combination with chromatography-mass spectrometry, represented by the following classes of compounds (in fractions): paraffins (29.7-29.9% of the total content of 13.8-14.0 mg/l), monoolefins (12.1-12.5%), dienes and monocycloolefins (6.11-6.09%), alkylbenzenes (11.2-11.0%), esters of aromatic acids (9.57-9.56%), alkylphenols (8.30-8.13%), alkyl-naphthalenes (3.87-3.78%), polyaromatic hydrocarbons (1.93-1.75%), fatty acids (8.10-8.13%), and also unidentified substances (3.50-3.57%). Due to the presence

in the composition of both BAVN and phytoadaptogens at least two common groups of physiologically active organic substances - polyphenols and fatty acids, it is assumed that there is a constellation of parameters of the neuro-endocrine-immune complex that respond to both types to the same extent. Adaptogens. A separate test was conducted to test this assumption in research.

The object of clinical and physiological observation were practically healthy people, individuals with dysfunction of the neuroendocrine-immune complex as a manifestation of maladaptation. Before and after a one-week course of using BAVN (10 people of both sexes) or "Balm Truskavets" phytoadaptogen (6 women and 4 men) were determined the main adaptation hormones, EEG indicators, HRV, phagocytosis, leukocytogram, as well as related parameters of bioelectrophotonics and acupuncture.

As a result of the screening, 39 parameters were found (18 EEG, 8 HRV, 5 biophysical, 4 phagocytosis, as well as the leukocyte adaptation index, triiodothyronine,

testosterone and cortisol), the physiologically favorable changes of which are common to both adaptogenic agents. Next, 39 parameters were grouped into 4

clusters, of which 2 are activating and 2 reducing (Fig. 30 and Table 4). In particular, moderately elevated levels of triiodothyronine, γ -rhythm SSC in the T6 locus, as well as LF and HF bands of HRV, entropy of the gas discharge image (GDI) in the left projection (H GDI L) and right-sided (positive sign of the symmetry index) asymmetry of the virtual third chakra completely normalize (cluster B+/A0). Instead, the levels of the adaptation index and bactericidal ability of neutrophils (BSSN) against both E. coli and Staph were significantly reduced. aureus, are significantly increased while still remaining reduced. At the same time, the moderately reduced levels of γ -rhythm SHSP in the F7, P4, P3, T6 and T5 loci and entropy in the T5 locus, as well as the GDI form factor in the right projection (SC GDI R) (cluster B-/A0), are completely normalized. That is, there is a normalizing (ambivalent-equilibrating) effect as one of the signs of adaptogens.

At the same time, normal levels of testosterone and four HRV markers of vagal tone also decrease, albeit slightly. This is accompanied by left lateralization (negative sign of symmetry/lateralization indices) of the initially symmetrical (quasi-zero symmetry/lateralization indices) γ -rhythm EEG, electrical conductivity of acupuncture points MC(AVL) and virtual seventh chakra (cluster B0/A-). On the other hand, normal levels of cortisol and circulating catecholamines (1/Mo as a HRV marker), sympathetic tone (AMo as a HRV marker), the activity of neurons generating γ -, δ - and θ -rhythms in 7 loci also increase, although slightly This is accompanied by a shift of the symmetry of the γ -rhythm to the right (cluster B0/A+).

Fig. 30. Clusters of adaptogenic effects common to Naftusya bioactive water and "Balzam Truskavets" phytocomposition. In brackets - number of parameters Table 4. Clusters of adaptogenic effects as differences between levels (Z+SE) after and before treatment Effect (30)

Clusters and Variables	Root/Variables correlation	Before (30)	after (30)	

B+/A0		0.65±0.14	0.02±0.05	-0.63±0.11
Triiodothyronine T6-	0.181	0.81±0.30	0.05±0.35	-0.77±0.28
ÿ PSD r PSD	0.145	0.37±0.25	-0.03±0.16	-0.39±0.20
LF band PSD		1.27±0.69	0.19±0.44	-1.08±0.58
HF band Chakra		0.51±0.44	-0.08±0.33	-0.59±0.30
3 Asymmetry Entropy		0.41±0.28	-0.15±0.24	-0.56±0.33
GDI Left B0/A-		0.53±0.21	0.15±0.20	-0.38±0.17
		0.09±0.05	-0.42±0.03	-0.52±0.05
Testosterone	0.208	0.23±0.29	-0.50±0.21	-0.74±0.36
SDNN HRV	0.179	-0.13±0.17	-0.46±0.10	-0.33±0.17
RMSSD HRV		0.14±0.25	-0.33±0.19	-0.47±0.17
pNN50 HRV		0.26±0.38	-0.29±0.31	-0.56±0.22
PSD VLF band		0.03±0.28	-0.39±0.23	-0.42±0.27
Laterality-ÿ		-0.07±0.17	-0.46±0.13	-0.39±0.20
Chakra 7 Asymmetry AP	0.204	0.17±0.22	-0.38±0.19	-0.54±0.23
MC(AVL) Laterality B0/A+		0.11±0.21	-0.57±0.31	-0.68±0.36
Cortisol		0.04±0.05	0.56±0.07	+0.52±0.06
	-0.182	0.05±0.27	0.64±0.23	+0.60±0.34
Asymmetry-ÿ	-0.162	-0.10±0.18	0.35±0.23	+0.46±0.25
T3-ÿ PSD a	-0.166	0.30±0.23	1.20±0.55	+0.90±0.40
F3-ÿ PSD a	-0.141	0.08±0.18	0.50±0.28	+0.43±0.24
T6-ÿ PSD a	-0.091	-0.04±0.19	0.87±0.57	+0.91±0.56
F8-ÿ PSD a		-0.04±0.13	0.77±0.51	+0.81±0.46
P4-ÿ PSD a		0.00±0.15	0.44±0.34	+0.44±0.23
C4-ÿ PSD a		0.00±0.13	0.38±0.26	+0.38±0.20
C3-ÿ PSD a		0.17±0.17	0.52±0.24	+0.35±0.19
C3-ÿ PSD a		-0.16±0.15	0.19±0.27	+0.35±0.17
Amplitude of Mode HRV 1/ Mode HRV		0.26±0.21	0.70±0.23	+0.44±0.25
		0.10±0.26	0.58±0.25	+0.48±0.19
Microbial count for Staph. aur. B-/A0		-0.16±0.11	0.14±0.14	+0.30±0.13
		-0.82±0.18	-0.30±0.17	+0.52±0.13
Bactericidal vs. E. coli	-0.349	-0.94±0.35	0.57±0.32	+1.50±0.35
Bactericidal vs. Staph. aureus	-0.332	-1.64±0.28	-0.47±0.27	+1.16±0.38
Killing Index vs E. coli	-0.164	-2.05±0.15	-1.73±0.16	+0.33±0.15
Popovich's Adaptation Index-1 T5-		-1.91±0.32	-1.08±0.36	+0.83±0.43
ÿ PSD r T6-ÿ	-0.097	-0.52±0.16	-0.32±0.15	+0.20±0.10
PSD a T6-ÿ		-0.35±0.06	0.05±0.21	+0.39±0.17
PSD r P4-ÿ		-0.55±0.12	-0.26±0.16	+0.30±0.16
PSD a P3-ÿ		-0.24±0.12	-0.06±0.17	+0.18±0.08
PSD a F7-ÿ		-0.19±0.15	0.00±0.22	+0.18±0.10
PSD r T5		-0.36±0.17	-0.04±0.17	+0.32±0.12
PSD Entropy		-0.45±0.27	0.06±0.16	+0.51±0.26
Shape Coefficient Right (f)		-0.63±0.15	-0.36±0.16	+0.27±0.14

No significant differences were found either for sexes (Fig. 31) or for nature adaptogens (Fig. 32).

Fig. 31. Individual and average ($M \pm SD$) changes of discriminant roots in women (F) and men (M), caused by the use of phytoadaptogen "Balsam Truskavets" (B) or bioactive water Petroleum (N)

Fig. 32. Centroids ($M \pm SD$) of discriminant roots of patients before and after the course of use phytoadaptogen "Balsam Truskavets" or Naftusya bioactive water

The presence of bacteria in the composition of BAVN, which are absent in the composition of the phytoadaptogen, gives the basis for the assumption of the existence, along with common/general, different/specific effects of both adaptogens on another constellation of parameters. Verification of this hypothesis became the goal of the next study on the same cohort patients As

a result of the screening, profiles (Fig. 33) of the normalized ones were created parameters, the levels of which differ significantly before and after taking BAVN or phytoadaptogen, as well as several parameters, which according to the following discriminant analysis also turned out to be characteristic, albeit insignificant the value of the Student's t test.

Further, by the method of direct differences between postprandial and basal actual effects of BAVN (as a complex of polyphenols, fatty acids and bacteria) and phytoadaptogen (as a complex of polyphenols and fatty acids), as well as simulated own (per se) effects of BAVN bacteria as the difference between average effects of BAVN and phytoadaptogen (Fig. 34).

Fig. 33. Profiles of Z-values ($M \pm SE$) of variables basal and after the course of using BAVN or balm "Truskavets"

Fig. 34. Patterns of actual effects of BAVN and balm and simulated own effects BAVN bacteria

The variety of effects of the complex of polyphenols (more precisely, aryl hydrocarbons Ah) and fatty acids (Fa) and bacteria are grouped into 10 clusters (Fig. 35).

The first cluster shows a weak stimulating effect on bactericidal ability of neutrophils by Ah&Fa, while the effect of bacteria is significantly pronounced. Amplifying effect of Ah&Fa on the relative SHSP alpha rhythm at the F7 locus, as well as on the neuro-endocrine stress indices of both Frolkis and Harkavy is as weak, and bacteria is less pronounced than in the previous cluster. Instead, on the next constellation

of 5 parameters (relative SHSP of the theta rhythm in the F7 and O2 loci, the entropy of the SHSP in the last locus and the entropy of the GRZ with a filter in

frontal projection, as well as Ch4 asymmetry) effects of both factors diametrically opposite - inhibitory on the part of Ah&Fa and activating on the part of bacteria.

Fig. 35. Clusters of topical effects of BAVN (Ah&Fa&Bac) and phytoadaptogen (Ah&Fa) and simulated effects of BAVN bacteria. The number of variables in the cluster is indicated in parentheses

Other parameters (alpha-rhythm index, relative SSC of theta-rhythm at Fp1 locus, aldosterone, calcitonin in women, phagocytic index and microbial count neutrophils in relation to *Staphylococcus aureus*, as well as the proportion of rod-like cells neutrophils) also increased under the influence of bacteria, although less noticeably, but under the influence of Ah&Fa they almost did not change. Parameters of the fifth cluster (relative SHSP of the delta rhythm in the T3 locus and theta rhythm in the Fp2 locus, lateralization alpha rhythm, as well as the proportion of monocytes) did not change under the influence of bacteria, but under the influence of Ah&Fa slightly decreased, while the symmetry of the alpha rhythm moved to the left. And the entropy of SHSP in the C3 locus, the level of calcitonin in men, triiodothyronine in both sexes, and Ch3 asymmetry in both situations decreased by significance limits. The seventh cluster is almost a mirror image of the fifth. In particular, the absolute SHSP of the alpha rhythm in the O2 locus, the lateralization of the beta rhythm, the neuroendocrine stress index of the author, as well as the energy of the first and third virtual the chakras under the influence of Ah&Fa did not change, but under the influence of bacteria they changed slightly decreased, while the symmetry of the beta rhythm shifted to the left. Eighth the cluster reflects a moderate increase in the relative SSC alpha rhythm in the T5 locus and of the absolute beta rhythm in the F4 locus, LFnu as a marker of sympathetic tone. GDI area in the frontal and left projections, as well as the energy of the second virtual chakras under the influence of Ah&Fa, instead, the same moderate decrease of the listed parameters under the influence of bacteria. Effects of both factors on the next constellation parameters have the same orientation, but are much more noticeable. This concerns of the absolute beta-rhythm SHSP in the F3, C3 and T3 loci, the Baevsky stress index, and as well as the area of the RHZ in the frontal projection when applying the filter. Last the cluster contains only one parameter - testosterone, normalized by sex and

with age, and reflects its moderate increase under the influence of Ah&Fa, instead, a significant decrease under the influence of bacteria, and to an almost equal extent in both sexes.

Calculation of centroids illustrates clear differences in the effects of adaptogens of different nature on the neuroendocrine-immune complex of both women and men (Fig. 36).

Fig. 36. Centroids (M±SD) of the discriminating roots of women (triangles) and men (squares) in the basal period and after a course of using Naftusya bioactive water or phytoadaptogen "Balm Truskavets"

By reformatting fig. 34, the patterns of the effects of the active factors of adaptogens on EEG parameters, hormones and neuro-hormonal indices of stress, leukocytogram and phagocytosis, as well as ARZ were highlighted (Fig. 37).

Fig. 37. Patterns of actual effects of aryl hydrocarbons and fatty acids and simulated effects of bacteria on parameters of EEG, HRS and hormones, immunity and RHV

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Canonical correlation analysis proves a very close relationship between neurotropic and endocrine effects of adaptogens (Tables 5 and 6 and Figs. 38 and 39) and between their effects on neuro-endocrine status and phagocytosis (Table 7 and Fig. 40).

Table 5. Factor structure of the first pair of canonical roots, which contain information about changes in EEG parameters and vegetative-endocrine regulation

Left site	R1
T3-γ PSDa	0.524
O2-γ PSDr	0.519
Fp2-γ PSDr	0.251
Entropy O2 PSD	0.225
F3-γ PSDa	0.224
C3-γ PSDa	0.174
F4-γ PSDa	0.165
Index of γ-rhythm	0.172
Laterality of γ-rhythm	0.057
F7-γ PSDr	-0.290
T5-γ PSDr	-0.192
Right site	R1
Cortisol	0.879
Frolkis's NH Stress Index	0.503
Garkavi's NH Stress Index	0.466
Baevskiy's HRV Stress Index	0.365
Aldosterone	0.230
Calcitonin normalized	0.150
Popovych's NH Stress Index	-0.395
Triiodothyronine	-0.129

$R=0.978; R^2=0.956; \hat{y}^2(108)=172; p<10^{-4}; \hat{y} \text{ Prime}<10^{-4}$

Fig. 38. Dot plot of canonical correlation between changes in EEG (X axis) and vegetative-endocrine (Y axis) parameters. The first pair of roots

The obtained data specify general provisions about cortical regulation sympatho-vagal balance and adaptation hormones. The cortisol level is positively regulated by theta-rhythm-generating neurons, which project to the O2 locus ($r=0.52$) and beta-rhythm-generating neurons, which are projected onto the T3 locus ($r=0.34$), as well as by the entropy of the SHSP neurons, which are projected onto the O2 locus ($r=0.38$). Instead, negative regulation is carried out

by alpha-rhythm-generating neurons that project to the T5 locus ($r=-0.39$). The aldosterone level is positively regulated by theta rhythm-generating neurons that project to the Fp2, O2, and F7 loci ($r=0.30$; 0.27 ; and 0.22 , respectively), and

is negatively regulated by alpha rhythm-generating neurons that project to locus T5 ($r=-0.22$).

Table 6. Factor structure of the second pair of canonical roots, which contain information about changes in EEG parameters and vegetative-endocrine regulation

Left site	R2
C3- γ PSDa	0.713
F3- γ PSDa	0.706
T3- γ PSDa	0.558
T5- γ PSDr O2-	0.537
γ PSDa F4- γ	0.336
PSDa Index	0.680
of γ -rhythm F7- γ PSDr	0.235
	-0.705
Entropy O2 PSD	-0.513
Fp2- γ PSDr	-0.319
O2- γ PSDr	-0.426
Right site	R2
Baevskiy's HRV Stress Index	0.746
Popovych's NH Stress Index	0.741
Testosterone normalized	0.718
Calcitonin normalized	0.460
Triiodothyronine	0.164
Folkis's NH Stress Index	-0.453
Garkavi's NH Stress Index	-0.402
Aldosterone	-0.316
Cortisol	-0.206

$R=0.946$; $R^2=0.895$; $\chi^2(88)=116$; $p=0.025$; γ Prime=0.002

Fig. 39. Dot plot of canonical correlation between changes in EEG (X axis) and vegetative-endocrine (Y axis) parameters. The second pair of roots

The leading (judging by the factor loadings) role of beta-rhythm-generating neurons, which project to the left loci of the scalp, was revealed, and responsible for the positive regulation of sympatho-vagal balance (T3, F3, C3, and

also F4; $r=0.73$; 0.65 ; 0.64 and 0.59 , respectively) and testosterone levels (F4, F3, C3; $r=0.49$; 0.47 ; and 0.43 , respectively). Alpha-rhythm-generating neurons projecting to the T5 locus exert a similar, but less significant influence ($r=0.30$ and 0.27 for sympatho-vagal balance and testosterone, respectively). Instead, the activity of theta-rhythm-generating neurons that project to the F7 and Fp2 loci, as well as the entropy of the SHSP neurons that project to the O2 locus, carry out negative regulation as sympatho-vagal balance ($r=-0.49$; -0.28 ; and -0.31 , respectively), and testosterone ($r=-0.51$ for F7). The level of calcitonin is subject to negative regulation by theta-rhythm-generating neurons that project to the F7 and Fp2 loci ($r=-0.42$ and -0.36 , respectively) and weak positive regulation by beta-rhythm-generating neurons that project to the F4 locus ($r=0.25$), as well as alpha rhythm activity in general ($r=0.29$). Finally, theta rhythm-generating neurons projecting to the O2 locus ($r=-0.27$), as well as the rightward shift of the symmetry of the alpha rhythm ($r=-0.34$), exert a weak negative influence on the triiodothyronine level. Neuro-hormonal stress indices of both Frolkis and Harkavy are positively regulated by theta-rhythm-generating neurons projecting to the O2 locus ($r=0.41$ and 0.36 ,

respectively), as well as by the entropy of the SHSP in this locus ($r=0.37$ and 0.33 , respectively), and negatively - by neurons that generate an alpha rhythm and project to the T5 locus ($r=-0.42$ and -0.38 , respectively). The author's proposed neuro-hormonal stress index has a greater number of significant correlations with the EEG beta-, theta-, and alpha rhythms of the SHSP (C3- $\dot{y}$: 0.47 ; F3- $\dot{y}$: 0.45 ; F4- $\dot{y}$: 0.44 ; T3- $\dot{y}$: 0.21 ; T5- $\dot{y}$: 0.41 ; O2- $\dot{y}$: -0.48 ; Fp2- $\dot{y}$: -0.38 ; F7- $\dot{y}$: -0.37), which indicates its greater informativeness (sorry for immodesty). Taken together, changes in the activity parameters of cortical and subcortical nervous structures caused by adaptogens determine changes in the activity of the vagus and sympathetic nuclei, as well as the blood levels of the main adaptation hormones by 95.6%. True, an alternative statement has the right to exist, because it is known that neuro-vegetative-endocrine connections have a bilateral nature.

Neuro-vegetative-endocrine influence on phagocytosis, judging by the coefficient of determination, is also very strong (Table 7). It can be seen that the top position among the regulators is occupied by the author's (again, sorry for the immodesty) neuro-hormonal stress index, which positively regulates the content of monocytes in the leukocytogram ($r=0.36$), and negatively - the activity of phagocytosis by neutrophils, both gram-negative and gram-positive bacteria ($r=-0.46$ and -0.44 , respectively). Among the index components, only testosterone and calcitonin are included in the factor structure of the canonical root by the program, which duplicate its effects ($r=0.37$; -0.28 and -0.37 for testosterone and 0.49 ; -0.30 and -0.32 for calcitonin, respectively). Instead, neither the stress-limiting factor aldosterone, which correlates only with phagocytic indices ($r=0.31$ and -0.30 , respectively), nor the stress-realizing factors triiodothyronine and sympathetic tone, which are significantly correlated only with E. coli phagocytosis activity, were included in the factor structure. ($r=-0.30$ and -0.36 , respectively).

All EEG parameters included in the factor structure are positively regulated

phagocytosis activity. Table 7. Factor structure of canonical roots that contain information about changes parameters of neuro-endocrine regulation and phagocytosis

Left site	R
Popovych's NH Stress Index	-0.626
Testosterone normalized	-0.537
Calcitonin normalized	-0.462
Frolkis's NH Stress Index	0.523
Fp2- γ PSDr	0.739
O2- γ PSDr	0.375
Entropy C3 PSD	0.429
Entropy O2 PSD	0.365
T3- γ PSDr	0.343
T7- γ PSDr	0.550
Right site	R
Phagocytosis Index vs E. coli	0.883
Phagocytosis Index vs St. aur 0.659	
Monocytes -0.364	
Killing Index vs E. coli -0.384	
Killing Index vs St. aureus -0.255	

bioRxiv

$R=0.901$; $R^2=0.812$; $\hat{y}^2(55)=74$; $p=0.044$; $\hat{y} \text{ Prime}=0.027$

Fig. 40. Dot plot of the canonical correlation between changes in neuro-endocrine (X axis) and immune (Y axis) parameters

However, on the part of theta-rhythm-generating neurons projecting to the F7 locus, as well as the entropy of SHSP in the C3 locus, influences in relation to two types of bacteria expressed to almost the same extent ($r=0.42$ and 0.44 and 0.27 and 0.36 , respectively). Instead, on the part of theta-rhythm-generating neurons projecting to the loci

Fp2 and O2, as well as the entropy of SHSP in the O2 locus regulatory effects on E. coli the following prevail in relation to Staph. aureus ($r=0.59$ and 0.40 ; 0.31 and 0.21 ; and 0.32 and 0.24 in accordance). In addition, delta-rhythm-generating neurons projecting to

locus T3, have a weak effect only on the activity of E. coli phagocytosis ($r=0.27$). Relationships of the intensity of phagocytosis with neuro-hormonal parameters more or less completely duplicate such activities of phagocytosis, therefore, apparently, they were not

included by the program in the factorial structure of the canonical root. For the third the parameter of phagocytosis - completeness - revealed significant connections only with the level of testosterone ($r=0.31$) and SSC Fp2- $\dot{y}$ ($r=-0.31$) in relation to E. coli and SSC F7- $\dot{y}$ ($r=-0.32$) regarding Staph. aureus, that is, of the opposite direction relative to the first two parameters of phagocytosis. The consequence of such diversity of regulatory effects is lack of correlation with the integral parameter of phagocytosis – bactericidal ability of neutrophils. Taken together, changes in neuro-hormonal regulation determine changes in the parameters of phagocytosis and leukocytogram by 81% (Fig. 40).

It turned out that changes in the parameters of the neuro-endocrine-immune complex significantly related to changes in bioelectrophotonics parameters (Table 8 and Fig. 41).

Table 8. Factor structure of canonical roots that contain information about changes parameters of bioelectrophotonics and neuro-endocrine-immune complex

Left site	R
Area GDI Frontal (f)	0.665
Area GDI Frontal	0.498
Chakra 2 Energy	0.630
Chakra 1 Energy	0.346
Entropy GDI Frontal (f)	-0.489
Right site	R
Phagocytosis Index vs St. aur. -0.721	
Frolov's NH Stress Index is -0.604	
Shavits NH Stress Index	-0.547
F7- $\dot{y}$ SDr	-0.237
F7- $\dot{y}$ SDr	-0.103
Triiodothyronine	0.418
Shavits NH Stress Index	0.356

123456789101112131415161718192021222324252627282930313233343536373839404142434445464748495051525354555657585960616263646566676869707172737475767778798081828384858687888990919293949596979899100

$R=0.822$; $R^2=0.675$; $\dot{y}$ (35)=50; $p=0.044$; $\dot{y}$ Prime=0.107

Fig. 41. Dot plot of the canonical correlation between changes in gas discharge imaging parameters (axis X) and neuro-endocrine-immune complex (axis Y)

Therefore, BAVN and phytoadaptogen affect a certain constellation of parameters similar effects due to the presence in their composition of at least of polyphenols/aryl hydrocarbons and fatty acids, instead, they are significant differ from each other in their influence on another constellation of parameters that due to at least the presence in the BAVN composition of microbes that are not present in the composition phytoadaptogen. By the way, the third most numerous constellation registered parameters EEG, HRV and HRV does not respond to any adaptogen, which is quite natural, since they are not hard pharmacokons = poisons, but "soft power", that is why it did not become object of analysis.

However, the intrinsic effects of aryl hydrocarbons and fatty acids remained unclear acids This became possible after the addition of a group of 7 to the previous cohort volunteers (4 women 45÷70 years old and 3 men 23÷54 years old) who used the extract Boryslav ozokerite (produced by Verba scientific company, Kyiv).

According to calculations, the daily intake of organic substances (as Corg) from BAVN is 0.3 mg/kg (bolus 3.2 ml/kg•3 times•0.03 mg/ml). Receipt of similar dose of organic substances is achieved with a single use of 2 ml of extract ozokerite, which contain 21.6 mg of Corg. By the way, the extract of ozokerite is currently available is legally used as a branded food bioactive additive "Immunan", as well as "Balm Truskavets".

Back in 1988, it was shown in our laboratory that in an environment containing ozokerite and the artificial salt analogue of Naftusi, during the 28-day monitoring fatty acids were not detected, on the contrary, already on the 6th day after the introduction of medium for cultivation of hydrocarbon-oxidizing bacteria isolated from BAVN, v fatty acids (C9-C18) appeared in it in a concentration of about 5 µM/l, which grew until the end of the 28-day cultivation of bacteria [M.S. Yaremenko and others, 1989]. Therefore, the effects of ozokerite extract can be attributed to at least aryl hydrocarbons, but not fatty acids.

Following the previous algorithm, we discovered 8 patterns effects of the three main operating principles of BAVN (Fig. 42).

Levels of triiodothyronine and calcitonin, vagal tone (HRV markers SDNN, RMSSD and pNN50), SHSP of delta rhythm-generating neurons that project to loci T3, F3 and C3, as well as the symmetry of the delta rhythm are subject to positive regulation aryl hydrocarbons and almost mirror negative regulation by fatty acids acids in the complete absence of bacterial influence. Aryl

hydrocarbons also positively regulate the amplitude of the beta rhythm, the bactericidal ability of neutrophils against E. coli and the intensity of phagocytosis of Staph. aureus, as well as SHSP of beta-rhythm-generating neurons that project to loci O1 and Fp2.

The first three parameters are also subject to positive regulatory influence from the side of bacteria, instead of the negative influence from the side of fatty acids. And the last two parameters are negatively regulated by both fatty acids and bacteria.

Another large constellation of parameters does not respond to aryl hydrocarbons, but subject to positive regulation by fatty acids and negative regulation by bacteria. This is, first of all, the so-called "activity of regulatory systems" according to R.M. Baevsky. and them component - sympathetic tone, testosterone level, SHSP beta-rhythm-generating neurons that project to loci T3, F3, P4, C4 and C3, as well as Entropy of SHSP in locus T5.

The fifth pattern is reciprocal to the first: index and deviation of the theta rhythm, lateralization of beta and alpha rhythms, Entropy of the SSC in the F3 locus, as well as SSC of alpha rhythm-generating neurons that project to the Fp1 locus are regulated positively by fatty acids and negatively by aryl hydrocarbons in full absence of bacterial influence.

In turn, the sixth pattern is reciprocal to the second: fatty acids also positively regulate the level of circulating catecholamines and SHSP neurons that generate beta-, alpha- and theta-rhythms in F4 and T5 focuses, and a negative effect on the listed parameters are performed by both aryl hydrocarbons and bacteria.

The seventh pattern is reciprocal to the third, reflecting the negative regulation of the beta-rhythm frequency, the alpha-rhythm index, the theta-rhythm SHSP in the F3 focus, as well as the level of rod-shaped neutrophils and the intensity of phagocytosis neutrophils *E. coli* aryl hydrocarbons and positive regulation as fatty acids and bacteria. Finally, the eighth pattern is reciprocal in relation fourth: bactericidal ability of neutrophils against *Staph. aureus*, SHSP theta-rhythm-generating neurons that project to the O2 locus, as well as Entropy SSCs in this locus are positively regulated by bacteria and negatively regulated by lipids acids in the absence of the influence of aryl hydrocarbons.

Fig. 42. Patterns of actual effects of aryl hydrocarbons and simulated effects of fatty acids and bacteria on the neuro-endocrine-immune complex of people

According to the set of described parameters of the neuro-endocrine-immune complex his conditions before balneotherapy and after its three variants are significantly different from one and retrospectively are unmistakably recognized (Fig. 43).

BAVN

6

BAVN

Fig. 43. Individual values of discriminant roots of patients to (B, small circles) and after a course of using BAVN (N, large circles), phytocomposition "Balsam Truskavets" (T, triangles) and ozokerite extract (O, diamonds)

It seems that aryl hydrocarbons, fatty acids and bacteria are able to modulate the activity of neurons, endocrinocytes and immunocytes through specific receptors. But about that later, and now about the experiments, the results of which, in fact, initiated the clinical and physiological observations, as well as supplemented and clarified the results of the latter. As early as 1989 [I.L. Popovich, S.V. Ivasivka, 1989; I.L. Popovych et al., 1990], a seminal

experiment was conducted on 108 Wistar rats weighing 140÷190 g. The animals of the main group (5 each in a cage) consumed ad libitum fresh Naftusya water (St. 21-H) from a graduated drinking bowl, on average $3.5 \pm 0.5\%$ of body weight, while the use of tap water in neighboring cages was $3.1 \pm 0.5\%$. According to chemical analyzes (Ph.D., Ph.D. Yasevich A.P.), the content of Sorg was 14.9 ± 2.9 mg/l, including fatty acids $0.01 \div 0.05$ mM/l, amine-containing substances $0.1 \div 0.5$ mg/l. In the second main group, an aqueous solution of organic substances isolated from Naftusi by the method of non-destructive lyophilic drying was used, which contained Sorghum 29.3 mg/l, including fatty acids - 0.52 mM/l, amino compounds - 0.55 mg/l. Voluntary drinking of such a solution turned out to be smaller (1.3% by weight), but due to the higher concentration, the daily dose of Sorg was 0.4 mg/kg versus 0.5 mg/kg in the first group. In the second control group, animals consumed deionized water. After the completion of the course (11 or 7 days) of drinking and daily fasting, the rats were subjected to immobilization-cold stress. At the same time, each animal was pushed into a dense cartridge with holes (proposed by Groisman S.D. and Karevina T.G.), which was placed in a refrigerator at a temperature of 2-4°C for 5 hours. After that, the animals were sacrificed by injection of Nembutal and the stomach, cut along the great curvature, was examined under a magnifying glass.

In control animals, stress caused expected mucosal damage stomach lining of varying severity in the area of the body and bottom (Fig. 44).

Fig. 44. Schematic representation of stress damage to the mucous membrane of the stomach, cut along the greater curvature, in rats of the control (upper row) and experimental (lower row) groups. Assessments of the severity of damage in points are given.

The relative frequency of damage was constant and was 80 ± 12 , 86 ± 12 , $83 \pm 10\%$ in different control groups, respectively. Among them, the frequency of ulcer formation

was 80 ± 12 , 57 ± 17 , $67 \pm 13\%$, respectively, and other damages were represented by multiple point erosions (the latter were, of course, accompanied by ulcers). The number of ulcers ranged from 1 to 11, the average value per animal in different control groups was 2.3 ± 0.7 ; 3.4 ± 2.0 ; 3.4 ± 1.5 .

At the same time, Naftusya's drinking of animals caused a tangible effect gastroprotective effect. Yes, after an 11-day course, stress caused damage to the mucous membrane in only 4 animals out of 10, and ulceration developed in only one animal, while in 10 control animals lesions developed were observed in 9, including multiple ulcers in 6. To achieve a 7-day course proved to have a similar preventive effect drinking, on the other hand, after a 3-day course, the effect was still not pronounced.

The gastroprotective effect of native Naftusa was, in principle, reproduced organic substances obtained from it. It was also found to be gastroprotective the effect of organic substances that enter the body parenterally is practical did not differ from their effect when administered orally. It was

these results that inspired us to think that Naftusia is not just banal diuretic and choleric, as it was believed for a century and a half (the first quarter of the 19th - end of the 20th century), but also one of the natural adaptogens with their wide range spectrum of physiological activity, as it was written in the textbook "Natural History" as early as 1721: "... the peasants of Truskavets and other Galician villages drink water mixed with oil for the treatment of many diseases." Indeed, the new is the well-forgotten old!

In order to verify the adaptogenic hypothesis, a comparative study was conducted an experiment in which, for 5 days, rats of both sexes were loaded through probe with Naftusya water (3 ml/200 g once), pure tap water, a also with the addition to the bolus of 0.1 ml of the adaptogen standard of ginseng tincture (old "Lubnikhimpharm") or phytocomposition "Balsam Crimea" (old state farm-plant "Nizhnehirskiy"), which was patented by us as an "Adaptogenic agent" based on the following experimental and clinical-physiological studies.

In addition, in line with the new concept of Ivasivka S.V. [Ivasivka S.V. and etc., 1990; S.V. Ivasivka, 1994; 1997] about the xenobiotic mechanism of action of water Oil that was based on the ability of both native water and extracted from it hydrophobic (but not hydrophilic) organic substances to shorten the duration of nembutal sleep, just as it is reduced by repeated use of nembutal itself, a separate group of animals received tap water from by adding 0.1 mg of nembutal powder.

The next day, the animals were subjected to acute stress, after which under light ether anesthesia, an ECG was recorded in the II century. taken from the incision the tip of the tail of a blood sample for counting the leukocytogram. In the final stage of the experiment, static muscle performance was assessed (by holding time on a vertical pole), after which animals were injected into the stomach through the same a probe of 4 ml of distilled water with 600 mg of phenolroth and placed in individual

plexiglass cages for 4 hours for the purpose of collecting urine with subsequent determination of the content of excreted phenol rot in it. This methodological approach, borrowed from Nakamura J. et al. [1977], made it possible to assess stressor damage to the mucosa stomach without sacrificing animals, which as a sign of our gratitude for the results demonstrated by them survived the 2 years assigned to them by nature comfortable conditions of the vivarium. Unfortunately, in the following experiments sacrifice was methodically inevitable.

As expected, acute stress was found to cause primarily ST-segment depression and T-wave flattening or depression, as well as shortening electrostoles (Fig. 45 and Table 9), which indicates pronounced myocardial dystrophy [Markova O.O., Popovych I.L., 1997].

Fig. 45. ECG of intact rats and rats exposed to stress against the background of receiving tap water. Options for typical (a), maximum (b) and minimum (c) changes are given

Table 9. Summary of discriminant analysis of parameters of electrocardiogram, mucosa stomach and leukocytograms of rats of both sexes intact and one day after acute stress on the background weekly use of fresh water and adaptogens of various nature

Variables and Roots (discriminating properties)	Correlations Variables-Roots		Intact rats (50)	Adaptogens +Stress (40)	Daily Water +Stress (10)
	R1	R2			
Root 1 (85.7%)	R1	R2	-3.24	+2.56	+5.94
Polymorphonuclear Neutrophils, % 0.381		-0.051	32.6	54.4	62.3
Phenolrot Urinary Excretion, %/4h 0.269		0.210	2.75	3.97	5.90
Monocytes, % 0.238		-0.025	3.65	7.43	8.90
R wave ECG, $\bar{y}V$ 0.084		0.122	330	367	476
S wave ECG, $\bar{y}V$ 0.061		0.104	118	135	201
Lymphocytes, % -0.428		0.014	56.9	34.6	24.5
T wave ECG, $\bar{y}V$ -0.191		-0.237	130	100	29
Eosinophils, % -0.078		0.040	2.84	2.06	2.00
ST joint ECG, $\bar{y}V$			53	44	-8
QT/RR ratio ECG, %			61.3	56.8	52.1
Root 2 (14.3 %) r	R1	R2	+0.39	-1.32	+3.34
wave ECG, $\bar{y}V$	0.121	-0.222	15	76	38
P wave ECG, $\bar{y}V$	0.067	-0.156	24.4	39.6	27.6
Static Endurance, sec	0.107	-0.122	21	60	51
Pq interval ECG, msec	0.034	0.083	55	49	52

Such changes were combined with an increase in the voltage of the R and S waves. At the same time, the urinary excretion of fenolrot injected into the stomach was twice as fast, which indicates an increase in the permeability of the damaged mucous membrane to it. Classic post-stress leukocytogram changes were reproduced: lymphopenia and eosinopenia combined with polymorphonuclear neutrophilia and monocytosis.

Since similar stress-limiting effects of the reference adaptogen and the candidates in this set were expected, at the first stage of the analysis, all four groups were collected into one, nominated as "Adaptogens". Further, as a result of the discriminant analysis, the centroids of the roots were calculated separately for each group with their visualization in the information space (Fig. 46).

Fig. 46. Centroids ($M \pm SD$) of discriminating roots of rats of both sexes in the basal period (O) and one day after acute stress, which was preceded by a 5-day intake of fresh water, Naftusya water, solutions of phytocomposition "Balsam Crimean", ginseng and [REDACTED]

A clear demarcation along the axis of the major root of the clusters of intact animals and controls reflects the previously described post-stress pathological changes in the permeability of the gastric mucosa, EEG teeth and intervals, and leukocytogram parameters. The displacement of the centroids of the animals of the experimental groups towards the centroid of the intact group reflects the stress-limiting effects of the applied means in the form of minimization or even prevention of deviations of certain parameters from the norm. And the absence of differences between the centroids of individual groups indicates a significant similarity of their integral adaptogenic effects. At the same time, along the axis of the minor root, the centroids of the experimental groups fall down from the centroid of the intact group. This reflects the expected increase in static muscle performance, as well as a shortening of the Pq interval and an increase in P-wave voltage, apparently due to the long-known sympathomimetic effect of adaptogens [A.V. Lupandyn, 1989]. However, the appearance was a complete surprise for us

additional tooth r (Fig. 45, a and c), practically absent in intact animals and little pronounced in control subjects (Fig. 45, b). It seems that this one the incomprehensible phenomenon is also a marker of adaptogenic (sympathomimetic) effect

Nembutal requires separate consideration. Judging by the localization of its cluster in the information space, the stress-limiting effects of nembutal are only a little differ from such ginseng, phytoadaptation and Naftusya water. In 1997 we associated the stress-limiting effect of Nembutal, and at the same time Naftusya water and phytoadaptogens, exclusively with their activation of microsomal hydroxylation [Markova O.O., Popovych I.L., 1997].

It is well known that hydroxylation is carried out by cytochromes P450 (P450) - a superfamily of heme-containing monooxygenases. A limited amount of P450 is participating in the synthesis of steroid hormones and bile acids from cholesterol, while most of these enzymes is involved in the oxidative metabolism of drugs, others foreign compounds and endogenous substrates, including the same bile acids and steroids These xenobiotic-metabolizing P450s mostly belong to of the CYP1, CYP2, and CYP3 families and, importantly, reveal a broad substrate specificity that sometimes overlaps [Buters JT et al., 1999]. Later, already

having own clinical and physiological data about neurotropic effects of Naftusya water and phytoadaptogens, as well as data from the literature about the existence of benzodiazopine and barbiturate sites of inhibitory GABA receptors of neurons of the CNS, we did not see much closer to the truth xenobiotic, and the neurotropic mechanism of the stress-limiting action of all four factors That is, if nembutal with a high probability realizes its stress-limiting effect through the barbiturate site of GABAA receptors of neurons tonsils, then polyphenols of phytoadaptogens and Naftusya water probably act through benzodiazopine site of the same receptors. The

obtained results finally convinced us of the belonging of water Naftusya to adaptogens and the expediency of further research in this direction.

In a separate experiment, we found out that the detected wide spectrum of the post-stress state of the gastric mucosa, as well as severity post-stressor changes in other target organs are significantly determined at least innate resistance to hypoxic hypoxia (estimated by the classic method Berezovsky V.Ya. [1975]) and aerobic muscle performance (estimated by classical swimming test of I.I. Brehman [1968]), as well as an autonomous state of the nervous system (estimated by the classical method of variational cardiointervalometry [Baevsky R.M. et al., 1984]). Therefore, in the future, experimental groups were formed from such a calculation that both the average values and the variance of these determinants parameters were the same.

In the following experiment, the effect of the organic component on the chemical one was clarified the composition of Naftusya water on the state of the neuroendocrine-immune complex and metabolome, as well as the gastric mucosa in rats of both sexes subjected to acute immobilization

cold stress. For this purpose, bottled table water was used

"Truskavetska", which is very similar to Naftusya water in terms of salt content and

of microelements and even a shaft of Sorg (Table 10), but it lacks hydrocarbon-oxidizing bacteria and the fatty acids produced by them.

Table 10. Chemical composition of liquids used for loads

	Daily (Control) Water	Truska- vets'ka Water	Bioactive Naftussya Water
mM/LN=10		N=10 N=10	
Approx ²⁺	3.4	2.15	2.9
Mg ²⁺	0.5	1.88	2.3
K ⁺	0.4	0.15	0.3
Na ⁺	0.5	0.31	0.6
HCO ₃ ⁻	2.9	7.72	8.3
Cl ⁻	3.4	0.28	1.0
SO ₄ ²⁻	1.2	0.26	1.0
mg/L			
H ₂ SiO ₃	5	9.55	9.5
H ₃ BO ₃	0.25	0.7	0.20
F	0.95	0.13	0.160
Br	8.3	0.074	0.034
J	0.025	0.125	0.004
C org	5.0	9.7	12.8
N org	0.02		0.33

Intact animals consumed fresh water from graduated drinking bowls ad libitum, an average of 2 ml/100 g. Experimental rats were administered the same fresh water for a week

water and "Truskavetska" and "Naftusya" waters through a probe once in a dose of 2 ml/100 g.

The next day, the animals were subjected, for bioethical reasons, to a less harsh one of stress according to the method of Nakamura J. et al. [1977] with our modification (placement in Plexiglas cage and immersion for 4 hours in water at 20°C to the level of the xiphoid appendage). A day later, a blood sample was taken from the tail of the rats for counting leukocytograms, re-registered ECG under light ether anesthesia, and immediately well, with a heavy heart, they were decapitated in order to obtain blood for analysis and sampling adrenal glands, thymus and spleen. At the first stage

of analysis, post-stress parameters of rats of both experimental groups was combined again in order to assess the role of the common components of the composition of both waters in their effects. First

of all, post-stress erosive-ulcerative lesions were reproduced gastric mucosa and EEG markers of myocardial dystrophy (Fig. 47). At the same time, stress expectedly caused a number of immunotropic and metabolotropic effects.

By means of screening, a constellation of post-stress parameters, divided into 6 patterns, was revealed, with subsequent calculation of the effects of organic substances as differences between the normalized effects of Truskavets waters and tap water (Fig. 47).

Fig. 47. Patterns of normalized parameters of the neuroendocrine-immune complex, metabolome, ECG, and gastric mucosa of rats one day after acute water-immersion stress, which was preceded by weekly exposure to tap water (DW) and Naftusya (NW) and Truskavetska (TW) waters (top), as well as the simulated effects of their organic substances - aryl hydrocarbons (Ah)

The first pattern reflects the ability of organic substances to reduce stress-induced depression of the T wave and ST junction and shortening of the Pq interval ECG, as well as a decrease in the level of eosinophils and alpha-lipoprotein cholesterol to the lower zone of the norm. And serum catalase activity and content in the splenocytogram lymphoblasts and macrophages, as well as the entropy of the splenocytogram are moved from from the lower normal zone to the upper one. On the other hand, organic substances are minimized induced increase of pbytherphonuclear content stress of neutrophils/microphages in the blood and Hassal bodies in the thymocytogram, as well as whole normalize the upper limit levels in the serum of catecholamines (VRS-marker

1/Mode) and corticosterone, lymphocytes in the splenocytogram and the microbial number of blood monocytes/macrophages. On the contrary, the microbial number of blood neutrophils/microphages, which is not subject to strosor influence, increases under the influence of organic substances, together with the activity of serum acid phosphatase. At the same time, another marker of cytolysis - aspartic aminotransferase, parameters of damage to the gastric mucosa, as well as the content of macrophages in the thymocytogram as a marker of immunogenesis activity were found to be independent of the influence of organic substances. At first glance, there is a contradiction with previous data on the gastroprotective effect of organic substances. However, if we take into account that due to the application of a stressor that was much milder than in the previous experiment, only moderate increases in corticosterone, catecholamine levels and sympathetic tone (see below) were recorded in this experiment, which caused much milder damage to the gastric mucosa. (the average number of ulcers is 1.0 ± 0.5 compared to 2.3 ± 0.7 ; 3.4 ± 2.0 ; 3.4 ± 1.5 in the previous experiment), then the contradiction is only imaginary. This is consistent with the classic statement that the action of adaptogens manifests itself more clearly, the more noticeable the pathological changes in the parameters of the body. In addition, a slight potentiation by organic substances of the stress-induced increase in the bactericidal capacity of blood neutrophils/microphages and sympathetic tone, on the one hand, and a decrease in vagal tone, testosterone level, and the completion of phagocytosis by neutrophils, on the other hand, were found.

Fig. 48. Centroids ($M \pm SE$) of discriminant roots of female (triangles) and male (squares) rats intact and one day after acute water immersion stress, which was preceded by a week of loading with tap water and Naftusya and Truskavetska waters. The roots contain condensed information about the parameters that are subject to the same influence of both waters

The calculation of the centroids of the discriminant roots, in which the information about the described parameters is condensed, proves, firstly, the absence by definition of differences between the effects of both Truskavets waters on them, and secondly, the absence of gender differences of these same parameters in both intact animals and subjects acute stress (Fig. 48).

At the next stage, it was found out which post-stress parameters are affected. Truskavets waters are excellent due to the bacteria/fatty acid (Bac/Fa) complex. Screening of the registered parameters revealed another constellation of them, separated for 10 patterns (Fig. 49).

Fig. 49. Patterns of normalized parameters of the neuroendocrine-immune complex, metabolome, ECG, and gastric mucosa of rats one day after acute water-immersion stress, which was preceded by weekly exposure to tap water (DW) and Naftusya waters (NBAW) and "Truskavetska" (TW)

Algebraic difference between the effects of "Truskavetska" water and daily water reflects the own effects of aryl hydrocarbons (Ah), absent in tap water, and the difference between the effects of Naftusya water and Truskavetska water reflects its own the effects of Bac/Fa, absent in the composition of the

latter. It was found (Fig. 50) that the T and ST voltage of the ECG, the activity of catalase and acid serum phosphatases, entropy of the splenocytogram and the content of reticulocytes in it grow under the influence of Ah, but not under the influence of Bac/Fa. Intervals Pq and qT ECG and sympathetic tone also increase significantly under the influence of Ah, but moderately are reduced under the influence of Bac/Fa. Serum creatine phosphokinase activity, the content of non-alpha-lipoprotein cholesterol, sodium in erythrocytes and theophylline-resistant T-lymphocytes in the blood change under the influence of Bac/Fa such to the same extent, and barely grow under the influence of Ah. Intensity stands out of monocyte/macrophage phagocytosis, which is moderately enhanced by Ah, but profound suppressed by Bac/Fa. On the other hand, the parameters of gastric mucosa damage, the content of macrophages in the thymus and T- and natural killers in the blood, neither Ah nor Bac/Fa affect Neutrophil phagocytosis completion and serum levels

catecholamines and corticosterone are also not under the influence of Ah, but very moderately decrease under the influence of Bac/Fa. Conversely, the latter do not affect electrical systole and the blood level of polymorphonuclear neutrophils, which are subject to the stimulating effect of Ah. The latter, in turn, do not affect the activity and intensity of phagocytosis of blood neutrophils/microphages, nor the entropy of the thymocytogram, nor the vagal tone, while Bac/Fa increase the activity of phagocytosis drastically, and the levels of the other three parameters moderately. Bac/Fa have a similar moderate effect on the phagocytosis activity of blood monocytes/macrophages and the content of Hassal's bodies in the thymus, while these parameters decrease under the influence of Ah.

Fig. 50. Patterns of simulated preventive effects on post-stress parameters of neuroendocrine-immune complex, metabolome, ECG and gastric mucosa of rats of aryl hydrocarbons and bacteria/fatty acid complex

The average values of clusters of post-stress parameters, as well as the effects of Ah and Bac/Fa are shown in fig. 51.

Fig. 51. Clusters of post-stress parameters of the neuroendocrine-immune complex, metabolome, ECG and gastric mucosa of rats against the background of drinking tap water (DW) and Naftusya water (BAWN) and "Truskavetska" (TW), as well as the effects of aromatic hydrocarbons (Ah) modeled on their basis and Naftusya water fatty acid/bacteria complex. The numbers indicate the number of parameters in clusters

Following the algorithm, the information about the described normalized parameters was condensed in three discriminant roots (Table 10 and Fig. 52).

Table 10. Parameters of neuroendocrine-immune complex, metabolome, ECG and mucosa stomach (included in the discriminative model and extra-model) of intact rats and a day after of acute water-immersion stress against the background of 7-day use of fresh water and water "Truskavetska" and Naftusya

Variables	Correlations			NWS (10)	TWS (10)	CWS (10)	Intact (10)
	Variables-Canonical	Roots	Roots				
Root 1 (64.0%)	Root 1	Root 2	Root 3	-8.4	-1.2	+3.0	+6.6
Phagocytosis Index of Neutrophils	-0.126	-0.100	0.171	2.15	-0.35	-0.09	0
Microbial Count of Neutrophils				1.25	0.42	0.19	0
Hassal's corpuscles of Thymus	-0.055	0.060	0.132	1.61	0.46	1.53	0
Natural Killer Lymphocytes of Blood	-0.049	0.055	-0.020	1.06	1.03	0.80	0
Reticulocytes of Spleen	-0.043	-0.005	-0.048	0.90	0.75	0.00	0
Entropy of Thymocytogram				0.83	0.25	0.58	0
Gastric Mucosa Injuries Index	-0.071	0.089	-0.027	1.05	1.04	0.85	0
Gastric Ulcers Length	-0.049	0.060	-0.004	0.74	0.67	0.61	0
MxDMn HRV as Vagal Tone				-0.09	-0.56	-0.48	0
QT/RR ratio ECG	0.089	-0.005	0.051	-1.36	-0.96	-0.25	0
Non-Lipoproteins	0.071	-0.000	-0.090	-1.40	-0.26	-0.54	0
Killing Index of Neutrophils, %	0.064	-0.001	-0.013	-1.11	-0.52	-0.30	0
1/AMo HRV as Catecholamines				-0.15	+0.50	+0.63	0
Root 2 (25.5%)	Root 1	Root 2	Root 3	-2.1		+2.0	+4.6
T wave ECG	-0.013	-0.177	-0.149		-0.56	-0.69	-2.68
ST joint ECG	-0.025	-0.131	-0.167		-0.14	-0.02	-1.63
Pq interval ECG	0.012	-0.120	-0.174		-1.00	-0.32	-2.33
QT interval ECG	0.032	-0.069	-0.214		-0.90	0.09	-1.18
Catalase	0.024	-0.091	0.009		0.19	0.13	-0.70
Theophylline-susceptible T-Lymphocytes	0.006	-0.112	-0.026		-0.33	-0.58	-0.95
Corticosterone	0.065	0.113	-0.063		-0.62	0.38	0.58

Polymorphonuclear Neutrophils of Blood	-0.027 0.020 1.26 1.38 1.83 0	0.084					
Macrophages of Thymus	-0.033 -0.016 0.77 0.96 0.95 0	0.077					
Root 3 (10.5%)		Root 1	Root 2	Root 3	+1.3	-3.6	+2.3 0.0
Entropy of Splenocytogram	-0.043 -0.021 -0.152 0.42 0.79 -0.42 0						
Sodium of Erythrocytes	0.044 0.027 -0.116 -0.74 0.24 -0.18 0						
Microbial Count of Monocytes	-1.51 1.38 0.59 0						
Acid Phosphatase	1.03 1.27 0.14 0	-0.043	0.008	-0.083			
Creatine Phosphokinase	0.18 0.91 0.46 0	-0.007	0.061	-0.074			
Amo HRV as Sympathetic Tone	+0.16 +1.36 +0.50 0	-0.072	0.131	-0.069			
Gastric Ulcers Amount	0.55 0.66 0.55						
Theophylline-resistant T-Lymphocytes	1.32 2.53 2.04	-0.023	0.085	-0.050			0
Phagocytosis Index of Monocytes	0.00 -0.61 0.38	0.013	0.009	0.137			0

Fig. 52. Individual values of discriminant roots of intact rats (I) and one day after of acute water-immersion stress, which was preceded by weekly use of fresh water (CWS), "Truskavetska" water (TS) and Naftusya water (NS)

As you can see, in the information space of the three discriminant roots, the animals of all groups are clearly separated from each other. And the localization of the centroids visualizes the absence of sexual dimorphism (Fig. 53).

Fig. 53. Centroids of discriminant roots of female (triangles) and male (squares) intact rats and one day after acute water immersion stress, which was preceded by a week of fresh water, Truskavetska water, and Naftusya water

A very close canonical correlation was found between neuro-endocrine parameters, on the one hand, and parameters of immunity, metabolome, ECG, and gastric mucosa, on the other (Fig. 54).

R=0.983; $R^2=0.967$; $\bar{y}$ Fig. 54. Dot plot $\chi^2(216)=301$; $p=0.0001$; $\bar{y}$ Prime $<10^{-6}$

of canonical correlation between neuro-endocrine parameters (X axis) and immunity, metabolome, ECG and gastric mucosa parameters (Y axis) of rats of both sexes

Previously, it was shown in our laboratory that as a result of a 28-day incubation of hydrocarbon-oxidizing bacteria isolated from BAVN in an environment that contained hydrocarbons of various origins, primarily from water-bearing rock, as well as ozokerite and oil from the nearby (about 6 km) Boryslav deposit and paraffin oil, biologically active substances appear in the culture fluids, which reproduce the inhibitory effect of BAVN on the activity of Na,K-ATPase of rat intestinal epitheliocytes and the motility of the smooth muscles of the mouse intestine, and the activating effect on the contractility of the isolated frog heart. Fatty acids (C11-C15) were identified among the biologically active substances of culture fluids [Yaremenko M.S. and others, 1988; 1989; Ivasivka S.V. et al., 1999].

This phenomenon prompted us to conduct the following experiment with the aim of comparative evaluation of the effects of native Naftusi and organic substances produced by its hydrocarbon-oxidizing bacteria. Only females were involved in the experiment, but this is not important given the previously stated lack of sexual dimorphism in balneoreactions. Other design features include the inclusion of fecal microflora components in the battery of tests and the exclusion of neuro-hormonal and metabolic parameters. Since the rats of the control group received the same tap water through a metal probe as the intact rats from the drinking bowl, the changes detected in them should be attributed

at the expense of chronic aversive (unpleasant) stress. Avoiding a discussion about the correctness of the terms, we will refer to the Ukrainian luminary Reznikov O.H. [2004; 2019], who, in order to develop chronic stress in female rats, conducted one-hour immobilization or simulated zoosocial conflict for 6 days.

The most noticeable were the decrease in the mass of the thymus and the content of eosinophils in the leukocytogram (Fig. 55).

Fig. 55. Patterns of normalized parameters of the endocrine-immune complex and microbiota of female rats after loading with tap water (DW), Naftusya water (NBAW) and culture fluid (CF) (top), as well as simulated effects of organic substances (Fa&Ah) and bacteria

Less pronounced immunotropic effects of chronic stress are a decrease in the absolute content of leukocytes in the blood and the relative content of B-lymphocytes, the microbial number of blood neutrophils/microphages and their bactericidal ability, the fate of plasma cells and lymphoblasts in the splenocytogram. On the other hand, the microbial number

blood monocytes/macrophages and their bactericidal capacity, relative content in the blood

theophylline-resistant T-lymphocytes, as well as the mass of the spleen moderately increase.

This is accompanied by a moderate thickening of the reticular and glomerular, but not fascicular, zones of the adrenal cortex. Among the components of the faecal microflora, chronic stress caused an increase

of the content of ordinary E. coli and its strain with hemolyzing ability in the absence

significant changes in the content of lactase-negative strains, as well as Enterobacteria, Lactobacilli and Bifidobacteria.

All four groups of animals are in the information field of discriminant roots

the changes are demarcated (Fig. 56).

Fig. 56. Individual values of discriminant roots of intact female rats (I) and through day after a week of fresh water (DW), Naftusya water (N) and cultural water liquid (CF)

Assuming the algebraic differences between the changes caused

consumption of culture fluid and tap water (chronic stress), reflect their own effects of fatty acids and aryl hydrocarbons, and the differences between

by the effects of Naftusya's native water and its organic substances - the effects of its bacteria, primarily hydrocarbon-oxidizing, we get the following picture (Figs. 55 and 57, Table 11).

Fig. 57. Clusters of effects on the parameters of the endocrine-immune complex and the microbiota of female rats of stress factors, the complex of fatty acids/aromatic hydrocarbons and water bacteria
Oil The numbers indicate the number of parameters in the cluster

Table 11. Parameters of the endocrine-immune complex and microbiota of intact female rats and after 5 days of fresh water (DW), Naftusya water (NW) and culture fluid (CF)

Variables	Correlations			CF (5)	DW (5)	NW (10)	Intact (19)
	Root 1	Root 2	Root 3				
Root 1(70%)	Root 1	Root 2	Root 3	-10.1	-0.05	+1.71	+1.77
Reticulocytes of Thymus, %	-0.066	0.093		0.108	5.60	4.60	-0.025
Fascicular Zone of Adrenal Cortex, μ M	-0.052	0.046		433	382	-0.064	4.00
Lymphoblasts of Spleen, %	-0.026	0.057		3.40	34.6	31.6	0.044
Theophilline Resistance T-Lymphocytes, %				0.052	0.030		32.9
Lymphocytes of Thymus, %	69.0	69.7	0.041	-0.173	0.166	4.1	
Microbian Count of Monocytes, B/Phagoc Root						8.2	4.6
2(24%)	Root 1	Root 2	Root 3	+0.55	-3.77	+3.40	-0.94
B-Lymphocytes of Blood, %	0.005	0.227	0.130	15.8	14.0	18.5	14.7
Plasmocytes of Spleen, %	0.022	0.171	0.117	1.80	1.60	2.70	1.74
Bactericidity of Neutrophils, 10 ⁹ Bacter/L Spleen	0.027	0.113	-0.032	14.4	12.0	19.0	15.7
Mass, mg	-0.019	0.087	0.203	1088	1084	1190	911
Bifidobacteria, lg CFU/g	0.048	0.082	0.084	8.20	8.40	8.70	8.42
Lactobacilli, lg CFU/g					6.80	7.00	7.60
Theophilline Sensitive T-Lymphocytes, %					14.8	13.4	16.5
Glomerular Zone of Adrenal Cortex, μ M					203	182	207
Macrophages of Thymus, % 0-	-0.047	-0.232	-0.125	3.00	3.20	1.50	2.84
Lymphocytes of Blood, % E. coli	0.063	-0.215	-0.148	17.1	25.2	16.8	25.2
hemolytic, lg CFU/g Pan-	0.024	-0.170	0.005	1.06	3.78	0.53	2.53
Lymphocytes of Blood, %	-0.039	-0.096	-0.025	60.2	59.8	54.1	57.7
Plasmocytes of Thymus, % E.	0.021	-0.080	-0.016	1.60	2.00	1.60	1.89
coli Lactosenegative, lg CFU/g	-0.001	-0.042	0.036	3.92	4.19	3.32	4.18
Enterobacteria, lg CFU/g	-0.002	-0.025	0.046	2.00	2.00	1.80	2.16
Root 3(6%)	Root 1	Root 2	Root 3	-0.37	+2.37	+0.84	-0.96
Eosinophiles of Blood, %	-0.001	0.050	-0.313	3.80	1.60	3.30	4.00
Microbian Count of Neutrophils, Bac/Ph Thymus	0.011	0.104	-0.149	8.0	6.8	8.4	8.1
Mass, mg Leukocytes	0.019	0.111	-0.118	161	132	153	153
of Blood, 10 ⁹ /L Reticular Zone	-0.011	0.046	-0.108	16.3	13.8	15.8	15.8
of Adrenal Cortex, μ M E. coli common, lg					46.3	51.0	45.6
CFU/g Bactericidity of					7.46	7.59	7.51
Monocytes, 10 ⁶ Bacteria/L					73	124	77

The polyvariance of the own effects of organic substances (OR) and Naftusi microbes can be reduced to separate blocks. In particular, both factors exert comparable stimulating effects on the mass of the thymus, the content of plasma cells in the spleen, B-lymphocytes and theophylline-sensitive T-lymphocytes in the blood, as well as on phagocytosis by neutrophils/microphages of *Staph. aureus*. Levels in the blood of leukocytes in general and eosinophils in particular and lymphoblasts in the spleen increase under the influence of OR only, and on the level of theophylline-resistant T-lymphocytes in the blood and reticulocytes in the thymus, as well as the thickness of the fascicular layer of the adrenal cortex, OR has a stimulating effect, and bacteria - an inhibitory effect. Instead, OPs reduce the thickness of the reticular layer of the adrenal cortex, inhibit phagocytosis by monocytes/macrophages of *Staph. aureus*, reduce the content of plasma cells in the thymus, as well as common *E. coli* and its strain with hemolytic ability in feces, while these parameters are not affected by Naftusi bacteria. Instead, Naftusi bacteria cause a significant increase in the content of Bifidobacteria and Lactobacilli probiotics in feces, as well as lymphocytes in the thymus, while the effect of OR on these parameters is the opposite. Finally, the content of macrophages in the thymus under the influence of Naftusi bacteria decreases, while ORs are ineffective. Separately, it should be noted the absence of effects of both factors on the content of lactose-negative strain of *E. coli* and Enterobacteria in feces, as well as the mass of the spleen and the thickness of the glomerular layer of the adrenal cortex. A moderate canonical correlation of the morpho-functional state of the adrenal cortex with the stool microbiota ($R=0.642$) and a very close correlation with the immune status ($R=0.965$) were revealed. It is interesting that the effects of microbiota and adrenal cortex on immunity are almost not potentiated (Fig. 58).

$R=0.971$; $R^2=0.943$; $\bar{y}$ Fig. 58. Dot plot $\bar{y}$ (135)=314; $p<10^{-6}$; $\bar{y}$ Prime<10⁻⁵

of canonical correlation between microbiota and adrenal parameters (X axis) and immunity (Y axis) of female rats

In the next experiment, tap water, native Naftusya, that is, with living microflora, as well as Naftusya, in which the microflora was killed by ultraviolet radiation or removed by filtering through a membrane sieve, were used for watering rats. This approach made it possible to assess the contributions to the effects of whole Naftusa, firstly, its organic substances (OR), primarily the aryl hydrocarbon/fatty acid complex, based on the differences in the effects of germ-free Naftusa and tap water; secondly, the effects of lipopolysaccharides/antigens of bacteria according to the differences in the effects of Naftusi with killed bacteria and germ-free Naftusi; thirdly, the effects of live bacteria, based on the differences between the effects of native Naftusa and germ-free (Figs. 59 and 60 and Table 12).

Fig. 59. Patterns of normalized parameters of immunity and metabolism of female rats after exposure to native Naftusya water, subjected to UV irradiation and filtering

Fig. 60. Clusters of simulated endocrine, immunotropic, and metabolotropic effects of aromatic hydrocarbons and fatty acids (AhFa) of germ-free (filtered) Naftusi water, lipopolysaccharides (LPS) of UV-killed Naftusi microbes, its living bacteria in general, and VV-factor of bacteria in particular. The numbers indicate the number of parameters in the cluster

Table 12. Summary of discriminant analysis of immune, endocrine and metabolic parameters of female rats after a 5-day intake of fresh water and Naftusya native water and UV-irradiated or passed through a membrane sieve

Variables	Correlations Variables- Canonical Roots			Native Naftu- ssya	Daily Water (Contr.)	Radiated Naft	Filt- rated Naft
	Root 1	Root 2	Root 3				
Root 1 (69%)				-15.9	-4.4 0	+1.7	+12.2
Reticulocytes of Spleen, MI -0.085 -0.060 0.022				+1.60	0	-2.08	-2.11
Lymphoblasts of Thymus, MI -0.070 0.058 0.094				+2.04	0	+0.92	-0.22
Reticulocytes of Thymus, MI -0.061 -0.003 0.102				+2.45	0	+0.14	-0.15
Spleen Mass Index, mg/kg Body Mass -0.060 0.053 0.128				+1.96	0	+0.94	+0.21
NK Lymphocytes of Blood, 10 ⁹ /L -0.077 -0.047 0.164				+5.12	0	-0.64	+0.23
Asparagine Aminotransferase, μ Kat/L -0.037 0.103 0.097				+1.31	0	+1.26	+0.29
Alanine Aminotransferase, μ Kat/L -0.032 0.066 0.079				+1.55	0	+1.26	+0.30
Thymus Mass Index, mg/kg Body Mass currently not in the model				+2.41	0	+0.72	-0.23
Lymphocytes of Thymus, MI currently not in the model				+2.33	0	+0.44	-0.46
Endotheliocytes of Thymus, MI currently not in the model				+1.73	0	+0.09	-0.41
(Ku/Nau) 0.5 as Mineralocorticoid activity currently not in the model				-1.36	0	+0.07	+0.52
Corticosterone, nM/L currently not in the model				-1.03	0	-0.25	+0.69
Canalicular secretion, %/2h currently not in the model				+0.30	0	+0.65	+1.44
Mucrosomal Hydroxylation, -ln min currently not in the model				-0.26		-0.03	+1.65
Root 2 (21%)				-1.3	-5.0 0	+9.8	-3.4
Neutrophils of Spleen, % -0.007 0.229 0.105				+1.59	0	+2.98	+0.90
Entropy of Splenocytogram, *1000 -0.014 0.137 0.093				+1.72	0	+2.48	+0.84
Microbial Count of Monocytes, Bac/Mon currently not in the model				+2.14	0	+3.24	+0.48
Superoxide dismutase, un/mL currently not in the model				+2.37	0	+3.33	+1.71
Lymphocytes of Spleen, % 0.008 -0.213 -0.087				-1.53	0	-2.96	+0.29
Phagocytosis Index of Monocytes, % -0.010 -0.112 0.124				+1.09		-1.11	+0.80
Root 3 (10%)				+4.4	-6.5 0	-1.3	+2.4
17-Ketosteroides Urine, nM/200g*10 h -0.026 0.014 0.222				+6.21	0	+2.68	+3.52
Middle Mass Molecules, units -0.015 0.084 0.203				+3.27	0	+2.69	+2.07
Monocytes of Spleen, MI -0.034 -0.001 0.200				+3.87	0	+1.22	+1.82
Sodium of loaded Urine, mM/L -0.054 0.081 0.182				+4.73	0	+2.96	+1.40
Leukocytes of Blood, 10 ⁹ /L -0.019 -0.013 0.096				+2.23	0	+0.35	+0.94
Bactericidal Capacity of Monocytes, 10 ⁶ /L -0.037 0.055 0.092				+6.54	0	+4.24	+1.14
Diuresis, mL/10h*200 g currently not in the model				+2.35	0	+0.99	+1.56
Lymphoblasts of Spleen, % 0.043 -0.001 -0.100				-1.58	0	-0.27	-0.19
Bilirubin, μ M/L currently not in the model				-2.57	0	-2.26	-0.89
Diene conjugates, E 232 /mL currently not in the model				-3.33	0	-2.84	-1.45
Malondyaldehyde, μ M/L currently not in the model				-2.70		-2.51	-1.43

It was found that the bactericidal ability of blood macrophages, the activity of two serum aminotrasferase and sodium concentration in urine under conditions of water diuresis all three Naftusi factors influence unidirectionally, but differently: the minimum amount is OR, and the maximum amount is live bacteria. Instead, on activity superoxide dismutase of erythrocytes, the intensity of phagocytosis of blood macrophages, the relative content of microphages in the splenocytogram, as well as its entropy lipopolysaccharides (LPS) of bacteria act somewhat more noticeably than live bacteria. Stimulating effect of live bacteria on the mass of the spleen and its absolute content reticulocytes, and the mass of the thymus and the content of lymphocytes, lymphoblasts, reticulocytes and endotheliocytes in it is noticeable, while LPS is barely expressed, on the other hand, OR does not affect the listed parameters of immunity, and the content

reticulocytes in the spleen are even reduced. Live bacteria increase the level of leukocytes in the blood in general and especially natural killers, the phagocytic activity of blood monocytes/macrophages, as well as their content in the spleen, while LPS moderately lowers these parameters, and AR occupy an intermediate position in terms of effect. At the same time, nocturnal diuresis and excretion of 17-ketosteroids with nocturnal urine, the serum level of medium-molecular-weight polypeptides (MMM), as well as hydroxylation activity (estimated by the negative $\ln$ of nembutal sleep duration) and the rate of tubular secretion (estimated by the excretion of phenolroth) increase to the greatest extent under the influence of OR. The effects on the listed metabolic parameters of both live and killed bacteria are ambiguous. In particular, they significantly suppress hydroxylation and tubular secretion to the same extent and moderately increase the level of MMM, while diuresis and excretion of 17-KS are affected in the opposite way. ARs moderately reduce the content of bilirubin and two products of lipoperoxidation in the serum, and in the splenocytogram of lymphocytes, while the effect on these parameters of both bacteria and their LPS is much more pronounced. Live bacteria also moderately reduce the content of lymphoblasts in the splenocytogram, the serum level of corticosterone, and mineralocorticoid activity (estimated by the K/Na ratio of urine), but neither their LPS nor OR significantly affect these parameters.

Returning to fig. 60, it is impossible not to notice a significant difference between the effects of Naftusi with live and killed bacteria, especially for the parameters of the third and fourth clusters. It is suggested that such a difference is a manifestation of another factor, different from both OR and LPS, which is a product of vital activity (activity of living) bacteria, nominated by us as a tribute to tradition as factor VV (*vis vitalis*). Analysis of the literature shows that such a factor not only exists, but is not the only one.

First of all, in contrast to lactic acid bacteria of the intestine, which produce only short-chain fatty acids (acetic, butyric and propionic) via [Yoo BB, Mazmanian SK, 2017], hydrocarbon-oxidizing bacteria Naftusi produce long (γ_{16} – γ_{18}) and very long (γ_{20} – γ_{24}) -chain fatty acids [M.S. Yaremenko et al., 1989], the physiological activity of which is almost an order of magnitude higher than that of short-chain ones, judging by their toxic concentrations: 100 μM versus 800 μM , and is manifested even in pM concentrations [De Jong AJ et al., 2014]. We will remind that the content of fatty acids in Naftusya water is in the range of 28–92 $\mu\text{Eq/L}$ [Ivasivka S.V. et al., 1999]. The effects of fatty acids are realized through specific receptors. At least 6 types of receptors are known. In particular, GPR41 is activated by acetic acid, GPR43 by propionic acid, GPR109A by butyric acid [Yoo BB, Mazmanian SK, 2017] and other short-chain (γ_4 – γ_{10}) [De Jong AJ et al., 2014], GPR84 by medium-chain (γ_{12} – γ_{14}), and GPR40 and GPR120 - long-chain (γ_{16} – γ_{18}) acids [De Jong AJ et al., 2014]. In addition to their independent biological activity, long-chain unsaturated fatty acids can be oxidized with the formation of a constellation of lipid mediators, which through appropriate receptors

cause a wide range of multidirectional effects [Harizi H. et al., 2008; Das UN, 2011; De Jong AJ et al., 2014].

In the course of our research, it is important to note the fact that receptors to fatty acids and the lipid mediators generated by them are expressed, firstly, by almost all types of immunocytes (innate lymphoid, dendritic and

cells, macrophages, monocytes, neutrophils, natural killers, B-lymphocytes, and

as well as Th1, Th2, Th17 and Tregs subpopulations of T-lymphocytes), in particular localized in

gut-associated lymphoid tissue (GALT) [Harizi H. et al., 2008; Das

UN, 2011; De Jong AJ et al., 2014; Yoo BB, Mazmanian SK, 2017; Radzikowska U. et al., 2019]. Secondly, by neurons of the enteric nervous system [Yoo BB,

Mazmanian SK, 2017]. Thirdly, by neurons and endocrinocytes of the hypothalamo-pituitary axis [Harizi H. et al., 2008; Das UN, 2011].

All four groups are in the information field of the three discriminant roots
 animals are very clearly demarcated (Fig. 61).

R(21%)
R(100%)

Fig. 61. Individual values of the first and second (above) and the first and third (below) discriminant roots, which contain information about the parameters of immunity and metabolism of female rats after 5-day consumption of fresh water (k) and native Naftusia water (n) and UV-irradiated (r) or passed through a membrane sieve (f)

In this study, it was found that both humans and rats have Naftusya water significantly stimulates the proliferation of Lactobacilli and Bifidobacteria probiotics, i.e. exhibits the properties of a prebiotic. However, in a comparative experiment with using organic substances (fatty) produced by Naftusi bacteria acids together with aryl hydrocarbons) and native Naftusi was found (Table 11 and Fig. 55), that such an effect is caused by Naftusi bacteria, instead organic substances even moderately inhibit the growth of probiotics (as well as lymphocytes in the thymus). This is a real surprise, because it would seem that prebiotics long-chain fatty acids introduced with Naftusya water could serve microbiota as a weighty "food additive" to the short-chain ones synthesized by it fatty acids for their own growth [Kaur et al., 2021]. It remains only suggest that Naftusi bacteria somehow stimulate the proliferation of microbiota in another way.

In addition, hydrocarbon-oxidizing bacteria produce aromatic ethers acids and alkylphenols, and their biocenous companions - thionic acids and sulfate-reducing ones bacteria - sulfur-containing and nitrogen-containing compounds identified in our laboratory [Datsko O.R. et al., 2007; Ivasivka S.V. et al., 2010]. Later it was found in the water (only qualitatively, without determining the concentration, with a degree of probability of 40-70%) are the following heterocyclic compounds, derivatives of phenol, indole, pyridine and quinoline: bis-(2-methylpropyl ether) 14-phenyldicarboxylic acid; (2-phenyl-1,3-dioxolane) methyl ester of octadecanoic acid; Heptadecano 9-methyl ether acids; 6-ethyl-3-octyl ether of phthalic acid; 6{[3-(1,3 dihydro-1,3 dioxo-2H-isoindol-2-y1)propyl][(4-methylphenyl)sulfonyl]-amino]-methyl ether hexanoic acid; 2,4,6-trioxyphenylethanone; 2,6-bis-1,1-dimethylethyl-4-methylphenol; N-methyl-4-nitro-N-phenyl-benzamide; N-[(3,4,5-trichlorophenoxy)-acetyl]methyl ester of l-serine; Benzenethamine; 2-(2,3-dimethoxy-4,5-methylenedioxyphenyl-1)-1-methylsulfinol-1-methylthioethylene) [Shestopalov et al.

2013].^V as a preamble, we note that although the aryl hydrocarbon receptor (AhR) was initially recognized as a receptor mediating the pathological effects of dioxins and other environmental pollutants [Nebert DW, Bausserman LL, 1970; Poland A. et al., 1976], AhR activation by endogenous (bilirubin and biliverdin [Phelan D. et al., 1988]), pseudoendogenous (products of biotransformation by intestinal microflora tryptophan [Murray IA, Perdew GH, 2020]) and the same ecological ones (polycyclic aromatic hydrocarbons, halogenated biphenyls, polyphenols, indoles, flavonoids [Busbee PB et al., 2013]) agonists have important physiological effects, including regulation of the immune system [Quintana FJ, Sherr DH, 2013; Climaco-Arvizu S. et al., 2016; Yang X. et al., 2020] and endocrine [Andric SA et al., 2000; Li LA. et al., 2005; Ye L. et al., 2011; Trego ML et al., 2018] responses. Both adaptive and innate immune cells require AhR signaling at critical checkpoints. AhR signaling is considered a promising drug and preventive purpose, especially in cancer, inflammatory and autoimmune diseases. Binding

AhR with both xenobiotic and endogenous ligands leads to highly specific for the transcriptome of cell changes and to changes in cell functions [Esser C., Rannug A., 2015]. It is becoming more and more obvious that physiological activity AhR is nuanced, involving complex cooperative/competitive "interactions" and changing the AhR from a toxic mediator to an important physiological sensor homeostasis [Murray IA, Perdew GH, 2020; Avilla MN, 2020; Kou Z., Dai W., 2021].

In our opinion, among the given list of organic compounds with a large at least one AhR agonist is likely to be present. Seasonal fluctuations in the composition of Naftusya water of different classes are well known organic substances and bacteria. This is accompanied by fluctuations in her biological activity assessed by the effect on Na,K-ATPase of the epithelium, contractility smooth muscles v. portae of the rat, the intestine of the mouse and the isolated heart of the frog, a also the rate of bile secretion and water absorption during perfusion of the thin segment intestines of an anesthetized rat [M.S. Yaremenko and others, 1989; S.V. Ivasivka, 1997].

To continue this topic in the next experiment in the process of 3 months of the monitoring of the Truskavetsky field of Naftusya water was found to be significant fluctuations in both composition and biological and physiological activity of water 8 wells with which the animals were loaded during the week. Identified diversity concentrations of organic substances and their effects by the method of cluster analysis was divided into 6 homogeneous clusters-groups, including water control (Table 13).

Table 13. Summary of discriminant analysis of rat physiological and chemical parameters parameters of fresh water and Naftusya water used for the weekly load

Variables	Correlations			I (7)	III (16)	IV (4)	Contr (5)	II (12)	V (5)
	Variables-Roots								
Root 1 (70.8%)	R 1	R 2 R 3	-0.048	-6.2	-2.7	-1.9	-1.5	+3.4 +12.1	
Hydroxylation, -ln min of Nembutal sleep	0.372	-0.444		-4.26 +0.36	-4.48 -0.45	-4.44 -0.28	-4.36 0.00	-4.03 +1.20	-3.58 +2.83
(Ku/Nau) 0.5 as Mineralocorticoid activity	0.328	0.145	-0.169	1.35 -1.23	1.38 -0.96	1.36 -1.18	1.47 0.00	1.50 +0.27	1.72 +2.55
Phagocytosis, latex bits/phagocyte	0.206	0.052	-0.358	40.0 -0.01	37.4 -0.72	32.3 -2.15	40.0 0.00	40.0 +0.01	58.2 +5.06
Static retention test, Sec	-0.258	-0.111	-0.858 243	+4.93	+0.13	-0.81	0.00	-0.74	-0.63
17-Ketosteroids excretion, nM/10h				89 +0.30	83 +0.06	86 +0.16	82 0.00	78 -0.15	63 -0.82
Diuresis after 6 mL of water load, mL/2h				5.59 +0.19	5.22 -0.51	5.30 -0.35	5.49 0.00	5.11 -0.71	4.53 -1.84
Root 2 (12.6%)	R 1	R 2 R 3	-0.354	-1.0	-0.4	-3.5	+5.8	+0.1 -0.7	
Carbon organic, mg/L	0.042	0.078		13.3 0.4	10.9 0.7	21.9 4.6	5.7 0.8	12.0 0.8	15.5 1.9
Amines, µg/L	0.024	-0.144 0.028		180 69	323 90	590 203	20 2	258 103	508 224
Bitumen, mg/L	-0.008	-0.127 0.038		1.40 0.43	1.47 0.14	1.85 0.47	0.75 0.29	1.29 0.30	1.38 0.36
Polyphenols,				1.00	1.01	1.55	0.00	0.95	0.00

mg/L				0.10	0.44	1.16	43	0.00	0.37	0.00
Fatty acids, µeqv/L				61			53	41	53	51
				2	3		13	12	6	6
Choleresis, µL/h•g of hepar	-0.031	-0.431	-0.203	311	304	292	259	298	299	299
				+1.62	+1.40	+1.03	0.00	+1.22	+1.26	
Canalicular secretion, %/2h	-0.082	-0.347	-0.325	88.8	68.2	73.8	54.0	70.1	66.9	66.9
				+4.04	+1.65	+2.31	0.00	+1.88	+1.51	
Motility of v. portae, % of baseline	0.010	-0.241	-0.041	131	119	128	100	1.17	123	123
				+2.15	+1.32	+1.94	0.00	+1.19	+1.59	
Diuresis nightly, mL/10h				5.61	5.52	5.58	5.12	5.25	5.61	5.61
				+0.45	+0.37	+0.43	0.00	+0.12	+0.45	
Oxidizability, mg O ₂ /L	0.004	0.034	-0.021	0.79	0.88	0.83	0.99	0.71	0.99	0.99
				0.16	0.06	0.06	0.04	0.09	0.37	0.37
Swimming test, min	-0.136	0.233	0.652	151	191	193	200	182	130	130
				-1.61	-0.30	-0.25	0.00	-0.58	-2.29	
Water intestinal absorption, µL/h•g of gut				11.8	12.5	12.2	14.3	12.2	12.3	12.3
				-2.27	-1.67	-1.87	0.00	-1.89	-1.80	
Root 3 (10.6%)	R 1	R 2 R 3		-3.9	+0.8	+3.5	+0.6		+0.6	-2.1

Notes. For physiological parameters, the upper rows are actual values, the lower rows are normalized. For chemical parameters, the upper rows are actual values, the lower rows are their standard errors

Further, by applying discriminant analysis, clusters were formed visualized in the information space of three roots, in which 94% is condensed information about chemical and physiological parameters (Fig. 62). As you can see, the clusters are clearly demarcated already in the space of two roots. At thus, along the axis of the major root, the extreme right zone is occupied by cluster V, whose members are characterized by the maximum activity for the sample of microsomal hydroxylation, estimated by the negative natural value logarithm of Nembutal sleep duration [Hansch C. et al., 1987], activity phagocytosis of neutrophils, assessed by the absorption of latex particles, as well as mineralocorticoid activity, estimated by the K/Na ratio of collected urine within 2 hours after the introduction into the stomach of 6 ml of fresh water. Instead, the volume stimulated urine and nocturnal excretion of 17-ketosteroids were minimal for samples Members of the II cluster are inferior to V rats in the listed parameters cluster, but still prevail over control animals. In the opposite from of the control cluster, the members of the I cluster are located in the zone, which manifest maximum static muscular endurance for the sample, estimated over time retention on a vertical pole, volume of stimulated urine and nocturnal excretion 17-ketosteroids, instead of mineralocorticoid, which is minimal for the sample activity. At the same time, the last two clusters do not differ from the control one, which is illustrated by the mixing of the projections of the individual values of the root on its axis

Fig. 62. Individual values of the first and second (top) and the first and third (bottom)

discriminant roots, which contain information about physiological and chemical parameters of rats parameters of tap water and Naftusya water, applied for weekly loads

Nevertheless, these two clusters are separated from the control one along the axis of the second one the root. At the same time, the top position of rats of the control cluster reflects the maximum duration of swimming to exhaustion and enteral speed for the sample absorption of water during perfusion of the isolated loop of the small intestine in combination with minimum rate of bile secretion and tubular secretion (estimated by excretion with urine in the process of aqueous diuresis of fenolrot, introduced intramuscularly simultaneously with water load), as well as nocturnal diuresis and motility of the isolated portal vein. And the lowest position is occupied by the IV cluster. Additional delimitation of the latter occurs along the axis of the third root, the top position of which reflects the minimal phagocytosis activity for the sample and static muscular endurance. At the same time, along the axis of the second root there is a chemical separation parameters of the water with which the animals were loaded. The top position of the control cluster reflects the minimum concentrations of organic matter in tap water

РБА

$R=0.719$; $R^2=0.517$; $\check{y}^2(35)=51$; $p=0.038$; $\check{y} \text{ Prime}=0.291$

Fig. 63. Dot plot of the canonical correlation between the chemical parameters of water (axis X) and by the physiological parameters of the rats loaded with them (Y axis)

Given that it is an integral component of the balneotherapy complex of the resort of Truskavets - ozokerite - contains petroleum-like substances in its composition, common to those in Naftusi, the presence of common substances seems quite likely effects of both balneofactors on certain neuroendocrine-immune parameters of the complex In order to test the hypothesis, an experiment was conducted on 50 healthy male rats divided into 5 identical groups. The animals of the first group remained intact, using tap water ad libitum. Instead, the other rats received the same tap water and bioactive Naftusya water through a probe at a dose of 1.5 ml/100 g m.t. within 6 days. Another group of rats along with Naftusya water, she received three applications on the tail of ozokerite (t0 40-42 0y, duration of 30 minutes, every other day), and the last - only applications of ozokerite.

Based on the hypothesis of equal exposure, groups of animals that received water Naphtusya or ozokerite, as well as both balneofactors, were combined into a group "Balneofactors". Screening

revealed 40 parameters (3 HRV parameters, 9 endocrine parameters and 28 immune), deviations of the levels of which are significantly different from such intact animals control and main groups. In this experiment, an additional aversive the factor, in addition to the introduction of the probe into the esophagus, was the animal's stay in the narrow individual Plexiglas chamber for 30 minutes, which was necessary for carrying out the application of ozokerite or simulating it in animals that were loaded Naftusya water. Following the adopted algorithm, by the difference of normalized

parameters of the rats of the main and control groups, the own effects of the factors present in the composition of both Naftusya water and ozokerite, which are aryl hydrocarbons, were calculated. The variety of effects is grouped into 8 clusters (Figs. 64 and 65).

Fig. 64. Patterns of normalized parameters of the neuroendocrine-immune complex of male rats exposed to daily water (DW) and balneofactors (BF) containing aryl hydrocarbons, as well as simulated intrinsic effects of aryl hydrocarbons (Ah)

Fig. 65. Clusters of effects on the parameters of the neuroendocrine-immune complex of male rats under chronic aversive stress and the applied balneofactors (BF) containing aryl hydrocarbons, as well as the simulated own effects of aryl hydrocarbons (Ah). The numbers under the clusters indicate the number of parameters

To identify exactly those parameters of the neuro-endocrine-immune complex, the set of which in intact, control and experimental rats is significantly

differs from each other, the available information space has been exposed discriminant analysis. The program included only 23 in the discriminant model variables, including 5 thymus, 3 spleen, 6 blood, 7 endocrine and two HRV parameters. As we can see (Fig. 66), in the two-dimensional information space of the roots intact, control and experimental animals are very clearly demarcated.

Fig. 66. Mean values ($M \pm SE$) of neuroendocrine-immune roots of intact male rats, watered with daily water, Naftusya water, those that received ozokerite applications, and also ozokerite and Naphtusyu

Since the rats in the control group were gavaged with the same water that the intact rats consumed ad libitum and additionally kept for 30 minutes in a tight chamber, then the detected changes are obviously manifestations of a chronic aversive stress

Displacement along the axis of the first root of the centroid of the cluster of control animals relative to the centroid of intact animals reflects the stress-induced increase levels of parameters that are directly related to the root and, accordingly, the reduction of levels parameters related to the root inversely. Further shift of

the centroid of rats exposed to balneofactors and more pronounced than in the control (5.0 units vs. 2.8 units), reflecting the enhancement of stimulatory and inhibitory effects of stress on these parameters. Because aversion was similar, the detected parameter changes can probably be attributed to account of organic substances in general and agonists of aryl hydrocarbon receptors in

particular. The following picture emerges. Stress-induced increases sympathetic tone (AMo) and the level of circulating catecholamines and/or glucagon (Moda as an inverse marker) and decreased vagal tone (MxDMn) and decrease the size of the glomerular zone of the adrenal cortex is accompanied by an increase

the content of macrophages/monocytes in the thymus, spleen and blood and the intensity of phagocytosis by them *Staph. aureus* with a slight decrease in phagocytosis activity. Along with this, the content of lymphocytes in the thymus decreases, lymphoblasts in the spleen and macrophages/neutrophils, in the blood - theophylline-resistant T-lymphocytes in combination with by increasing the content of B-lymphocytes. The latter can be interpreted as an increase of the content of NK lymphocytes, the share of which among the latter is about 1/3, and/or as a decrease expression of CD3 and CD4 receptors by lymphocytes. In addition to adverse factors presentation of organic substances to the body from both the intestinal mucosa and of the skin increases the listed neuro-endocrine and immune manifestations of chronic stress.

Instead, the effect of chronic stress on a different constellation of parameters neuroendocrine-immune complex, information about which is condensed in second root, balneofactors are minimized, reduced to nothing or even is reversed. Quantitatively, this is expressed by a decrease in the shift of the second centroid root from 5.0 units. up to 3.4 units

Inhibitory regulation (downregulation) is carried out in relation to stress-induced thickening of the reticular and fascicular zones of the adrenal cortex and their mass, plasma levels of corticosterone and testosterone - on the one hand, and mass of the thymus and its contents of Hassal's corpuscles and epitheliocytes, as well as phagocytic activity of blood neutrophils - on the other hand.

Stimulating regulation (upregulation) is carried out in relation to mineralocorticoid activity and brain zone of the adrenal glands - on the one hand, and to content of reticulocytes in the spleen and thymus, endotheliocytes in the latter, rod-shaped neutrophils and NK-lymphocytes in the blood, as well as blast transformation of T-lymphocytes - on the other hand.

Calculation of centroids separately for groups of rats that received water Naftusya, applications of ozokerite or both balneofactors, showed complete no differences. Therefore, the modulating effect on the listed parameters of the neuroendocrine-immune complex of Naftusi and ozokerite, as well as their combinations, is practically equivalent.

However, it should be noted that in this experiment there was attention focused only on those parameters whose reactions are the same for both Naftusya water and ozokerite. This by no means excludes the presence of another constellation of parameters, the effects of which Naftusi and ozokerite, as well as their combination, are significantly different, and both in rats and in humans [Ivasivka S.V. et al., 2008; Popovych AI, 2018; 2019].

Finally, the canonical correlation between the mentioned neuro-endocrine and immune parameters was analyzed. Placement of sets along the abscissa axis (argument) and the ordinate (function) is quite conditional, because the nervous, endocrine and immune systems equally interact with each other through neurotransmitters, hormones and cytokines, the sources of which are simultaneously neurons, endocrinocytes and immunocytes.

Table 16. Factor loadings on neuro-endocrine (left set) and immune (right set) canonical roots of male rats

Parameters

Left set	R
AMo HRV as Sympathetic tone, % 0.924	
1/Mode HRV as Circulating Catecholamines, msec	- 0.698
(Nap/Kp) 0.5 as Mineralocorticoid Activity 0.371	
Corticosterone, nM/L 0.193	
1xDMn HRV as Vagal Tone, msec -0.866	
Adrenal Mass Index, mg/100g Body Mass -0.355	
Glomerular Zone of Adrenal Cortex, $\dot{y}M$ -0.301	
Fascicular Zone of Adrenal Cortex, $\dot{y}M$ -0.246	
Reticular Zone Adrenal Cortex, $\dot{y}M$ -0.184	
Right set	R
Macrophages of Spleen, % 0.864	
Hassal's corpuscles of Thymus, % 0.273	
Endotheliocytes of Thymus, % 0.271	
Rod-shaped Neutrophils of Blood, % 0.257	
Theophylline-resistant T-Lymphocytes, % 0.248	
Reticulocytes of Spleen, % 0.196	
Epitheliocytes of Thymus, % 0.194	
Macrophages of Thymus, % 0.185	
NK-Lymphocytes of Blood, % 0.172	
T-Lymphocytes of Blood, % -0.446	
Microphages of Spleen, % -0.406	
Phagocytic Index of Monocytes of Blood, % -0.350	
Reticulocytes of Thymus, % -0.217	
Lymphocytes of Thymus, % -0.192	
Microbial Count Monocytes of Blood, Bac/Phag -0.135	

$R=0.973$; $R^2=0.948$; $\dot{y}$ $\chi^2(209)=285$; $p=0.0004$; $\dot{y}$ Prime=0.0002

Fig. 67. Dot plot of canonical correlation between neuroendocrine (X-axis) and immune (Y axis) parameters of male rats

The obtained results, taken together with existing ideas about neuro-endocrine-immune interactions, give us grounds for the following speculations. At

separate or combined use of balneofactors present in their composition

agonists of Ah-receptors activate probably expressing these receptors macrophages of the gut-associated lymphoid tissue (GALT) and/or skin (SALT). Macrophages, in turn, secrete cytokines that excite chemoreceptors of both afferent fibers of the vagus of the intestinal mucosa and somatic nerves of the skin, along which impulses reach the structures of the central nervous system, responsible for the regulation of immunity and adaptation hormones. Cytokines can reach the central nervous system also through the blood. At the same time, macrophages secrete hormones, in particular CRH and ACTH, which exert both immunotropic and neurotropic effects.

In order to test the hypothesis that the effect of BAVN on the body is carried out by irritating the nerve endings, a special observation of two groups of patients of both sexes. One of them during 7 days used BAVN (3 ml/kg three times a day), and the second was exposed for 4 days transcutaneous half-hour electrical stimulation with the "VEB-1" device (patent owner V.E. Babelyuk).

The battery of tests used in previous observations was supplemented biophysical parameters of the skin, registered methods of electro-acupuncture and gas-discharge visualization (bioelectrophotonics). The basis for the registration of these biophysical parameters became the data we received about them earlier close correlations with the parameters of the neuroendocrine-immune complex [Babelyuk VE, Popovych IL et al., 2023].

By the method of discriminant analysis of the information field before and after the course stimuli, 26 parameters common to the effects of BAVN and transcutaneous were found electrical stimulation (Table 17). Parameter information is condensed in pairs canonical roots. The

regulatory (causal) root receives positive factor loadings from the γ -rhythm generating structures projected on the Fp2, Fp1 and F3 loci, VLF HRV range as a marker of subcortical sympathetic influences, stress index Baevsky as a marker of sympathetic tone, as well as 1/Mode as a level marker circulating catecholamines. Inverse components of the factor structure the causal root is, first of all, the EEG entropy in the F8 locus, as well as the neural structures generating γ -, δ -, and θ -rhythms, which are projected onto the Fp2, F7, and T6 loci respectively, together with two VRS-markers of vagal tone. In the

factorial structure of the root of regulated (dependent) variables by the program included testosterone (both actual and sex- and age-standardized) and cortisol along with 10 immune, 2 hemodynamic, 3 metabolic, and 3 bioelectrophotonic variables. The shape and symmetry of the gas discharge image, as purely biophysical parameters, do not require special comments, unlike from the virtual energy of the first modeled by the parameters of the glow of the fingers chakra, which according to the canons of Ayurveda is connected precisely with the adrenal glands [cit. for Chase CR, 2018], which at the same time are a source of testosterone in women, or testicles [cit. by L.G. Puchko, 2004].

Table 17. Factor structure of the canonical root, in which condensed information about common changes in parameters under the influence of electrical stimulation or balneotherapy

EEG/HRV variables	R
1/Mode HRV	0.495
Fp2- δ PSDa	0.445
F3- δ PSDa	0.434
Fp1- δ PSDa	0.416
Ln Baevskiy's Stress Index	0.231
Baevskiy's Stress Index	0.084
PSD VLF band	0.076
F8 PSD Entropy	-0.511
TNN HRV	-0.508
Fp2- δ PSDr	-0.316
F7- δ PSDr	-0.185
SDNN HRV	-0.137
RMSSD HRV	-0.129
T6- δ PSDr	-0.163
Endocrine, Immune, Metabolic, Hemodynamics, Bioelectrophotonics variables	R
Immunoglobulins A	0.468
Kerdoe's Vegetative Index	0.326
Testosterone standardized by sex&age	0.320
Shape Coefficient GDI Right (f)	0.297
Killing Index vs Staph. aureus	0.293
Popovych's Adaptation Index-2	0.282
Interleukin-1	0.220
Microbial Count vs E. coli	0.220
Blood Pressure Diastolic-3	0.195
Testosterone actual	0.185
Bactericidity vs Staph. aureus 0.180	
Circulating Immune Complexes 0.159	
Bactericidity vs. E. coli 0.140	
Microbial Count vs Staph. aureus 0.107	
HDLP Cholesterol 0.055	
CD3 +CD8 +T-cytolytic Lymphocytes -0.289	
C-reactive protein -0.255	
Symmetry GDI (f) -0.104	
Cortisol -0.074	
Chakra 1 Energy (f) -0.038	
CD3 +CD25 + T-regulatory Lymphocytes -0.034	

Total adaptogenic changes in cortical, subcortical and trunk activity structures determine the total changes of endocrine, hemodynamic, metabolic, immune and bioelectrophotonic indicators by 83.5% (Fig. 68).

R=0.914; R2=0.835; y

2
(308)=357; p=0.028; y Prime<10 -4

Fig. 68. Dot diagram of the canonical correlation between changes in EEG/HRV (X-line) and endocrine, immune, metabolic, hemodynamic and HRV (Y-line) indicators

As we can see, the reaction to both electrical stimulation and the use of Naftusya water occurs in all participants without exception, although the severity of the reaction is significant individual differences (Fig. 69), which is quite natural. Level reduction of the root reflects the growth of the levels of 13 variables related to the root inversely, and decrease in the levels of 7 variables directly related to it (Table 18).

Fig. 69. Individual values of the roots of women (F) and men (M) before and after the course of percutaneous electrical stimulation and drinking Naftusya water

No significant differences were found either by the nature of the adaptogen or by gender (Fig. 69 and 70).

Fig. 70. Average values (Mean±SD) of the roots of women (F) and men (M) before and after a course of transcutaneous e [redacted] and drinking Naftusya water (N)

For the completeness of the picture, other joint effects of adaptogens (Fig. 71 and Table 18) should be taken into account, which were not included by the program in the discriminant model, probably due to redundancy and/or duplication of information. By the way, the newly discovered second chakra in the table is associated with testicles/ ovaries [cit. according to Chase CR, 2018] or adrenal glands and ovaries [cit. according to L.G. Puchko, 2004].

Fig. 71. Clusters of modulating effects (Z±SE) of adaptogens. The number of variables in the cluster is indicated in parentheses

Clusters and Variables	R Before (57)	After (57)	Effect (57)
B+/A+++			
F3- $\dot{\gamma}$ PSDa	-0.146 +1.44±0.42	+3.97±1.56	+2.53±1.34
F8- $\dot{\gamma}$ PSDa	+1.53±0.45	+9.14±3.24	+7.62±3.11
Fp2- $\dot{\gamma}$ PSDa	+1.26±0.39	+4.39±1.70	+3.13±1.56
Fp1- $\dot{\gamma}$ PSDa	+1.81±0.60	+4.95±1.83	+3.14±1.59
B+/A++			
O2- $\dot{\gamma}$ PSDr	-0.152 +0.42±0.17 CD3	+0.84±0.20	+0.42±0.17
+CD25 + T _{regulatory} Lym -0.193 +0.40±0.13 Microbial Count vs E. coli -0.220 +0.61±0.13 +0.47±0.17 +0.68±0.18 +0.65±0.18		+0.90±0.20	+0.51±0.19
P4- $\dot{\gamma}$ PSDr	+0.50±0.33	+0.82±0.20	+0.34±0.17
1/Mode HRV	+1.11±0.34	+1.16±0.20	+0.47±0.17
Heart Rate	+0.42±0.13	+1.06±0.18	+0.40±0.14
Baevskiy's Stress Index raw		+1.18±0.45	+0.69±0.44
Calcitonin in Female		+1.94±0.56	+0.83±0.60
Electrokinetic Index		+0.53±0.13	+0.11±0.03
B-/A0			
F7- $\dot{\gamma}$ PSDr	-0.135 -0.45±0.13	-0.17±0.14	+0.29±0.12
Frequency- $\dot{\gamma}$	-0.166 -0.18±0.09	+0.12±0.14	+0.30±0.16
Kerdoo's Vegetative Index	-0.139 -0.08±0.12	+0.21±0.14	+0.29±0.16
Cortisol at all	-0.111 -0.72±0.13	-0.49±0.15	+0.24±0.14
Cortisol in Females	-0.85±0.10	-0.32±0.23	+0.53±0.21
Cortisol in Male	-0.59±0.24	-0.66±0.19	-0.07±0.17
Ln Baevskiy's Stress Index	-0.40±0.43	+0.52±0.43	+0.92±0.37
Shape Coefficient GDI Right (f)	-0.23±0.12	+0.06±0.13	+0.29±0.14
CD3 + CD8 + T-cytolytic Lymph	-0.80±0.19	-0.20±0.27	+0.60±0.26
Microbial Count vs St. aureus	-0.225 -0.32±0.10	+0.07±0.13	+0.39±0.13
CIC	-0.231 -0.69±0.11	-0.26±0.13	+0.43±0.13
B- -/A-			
Bactericidity vs E. coli	-0.303 -2.27±0.36	-0.63±0.34	+1.64±0.39
Bactericity vs Staph. aureus Killing	-0.287 -2.16±0.35	-0.62±0.36	+1.54±0.42
Index vs Staph. aureus Killing Index	-0.401 -2.20±0.12	-1.42±0.14	+0.79±0.20
vs E. coli Popovych's	-2.74±0.09	-2.09±0.10	+0.65±0.12
Adaptation Index-2 B++/A+	-1.95±0.13	-1.62±0.15	+0.32±0.16
PSD LF band	+1.28±0.44	+0.34±0.26	-0.94±0.37
Testosterone in Female	+1.60±0.55	+1.15±0.53	-0.45±0.24
AP MC (AVL) Right EC	+2.61±0.44	+1.99±0.23	-0.63±0.41
IgM	+1.15±0.17	+0.76±0.18	-0.39±0.22
B+/A0			
Asymmetry- $\dot{\gamma}$	0.158 +0.33±0.16 0.122	-0.02±0.13	-0.35±0.18
Interleukin-1	+0.62±0.19 0.071	+0.20±0.26	-0.42±0.27
IgA	+0.29±0.23 +0.24±0.11	+0.04±0.22	-0.24±0.14
Symmetry GDI (f)	+0.32±0.10	-0.22±0.17	-0.46±0.19
Chakra 2 Asymmetry (f)	+0.47±0.12	-0.10±0.12	-0.42±0.16
Chakra 1 Energy (f)	+0.73±0.19	+0.33±0.12	-0.13±0.05
C-reactive Protein	+0.84±0.36	+0.48±0.26	-0.26±0.06
BP diastolic-3	+0.50±0.13	+0.03±0.36	-0.81±0.33
HDLP Cholesterol	+0.65±0.16	+0.28±0.11	-0.22±0.07
Bilirubin direct		+0.20±0.14	-0.45±0.13
B0/A-			
F8 PSD Entropy 0.164 -0.14±0.15		-0.59±0.21	-0.46±0.21
Fp2- $\dot{\gamma}$ PSDr 0.160 +0.05±0.12		-0.21±0.09	-0.26±0.12
AP MC (AVL) EC Laterality Ind 0.166 +0.13±0.10		-0.14±0.12	-0.28±0.16

Pd3/Pd1 Ratio	0.145 ±0.15±0.08	-0.08±0.12	-0.23±0.14
P4-γ PSDr		-0.06±0.14	-0.40±0.10
T6-γ PSDr		-0.26±0.14	-0.50±0.11
O2-γ PSDr		-0.11±0.13	-0.44±0.11
PSD VLF band		-0.14±0.18	-0.58±0.13
PSD HF band		-0.18±0.22	-0.42±0.19
RMSSD HRV		-0.23±0.19	-0.50±0.13
SDNN HRV		-0.26±0.09	-0.47±0.07
pNN50 HRV		-0.27±0.23	-0.61±0.14
TNN HRV		+0.16±0.23	-0.23±0.22
Triiodothyronine		-0.19±0.23	-0.46±0.23
LDLP Cholesterol		-0.12±0.13	-0.34±0.10

The above supports the assumption that BAVN is an afferent stimulus fibers of the vagus nerve, which innervate the mucous membrane of the digestive tract, from where nerve impulses go to the regulatory centers of the central nervous system, which are at the same time the final point of impulse and from the nerve endings of the skin when they are irritated weak electric current, as well as ozokerite or mineral water for font In order

to find out the roles of organic substances, trace elements and electrolytes water in the modulation of the neuroendocrine-immune complex, an experiment was conducted on female rats loaded for a week with fresh water, BAVN, mineral waters of Sofia (Truskavets) and Herts (Bukovyna), as well as artificial salt analogue of the latter, which gave a range of Corg concentrations of 0÷34 mg/l, Norg 0÷0.8 mg/l, H₃BO₃ 0÷43 mg/l, H₂SiO₃ 0÷9.9 mg/l, Br - 0÷21.1 mg/l, J - 0÷6.6 mg/l, F - 0÷0.95 mg/l, HCO₃²⁻ 2.9÷8.2 mM/l, Ca²⁺ 2.9÷5.3 mM/l, Mg²⁺ 0.5÷4.3 mM/l, SO₄²⁻ 0.1÷13.1 mM/l, Cl⁻ 1÷205 mM/l, Na⁺ 0.5÷197 mM/l, K⁺ 0.3÷0.4 mM/l. The chemical

canonical root represents Norg to the maximum extent, but Corg to a much lesser extent and inversely (Table 19).

Endocrine root

reflects the stimulating effect of Norg on the plasma level of triiodothyronine ($r=0.45$) and situational (morning) mineralocorticoid activity ($r=0.27$), instead inhibitory ($r=-0.22$) effect on basal mineralocorticoid activity (estimated by the thickness of the glomerular zone of the adrenal cortex), as well as on the parathyroid activity, both morning ($r=-0.21$) and mid-day ($r=-0.20$).

Table 19. Factor structure of the canonical correlation between the roots that represent the content of organic nitrogen and carbon liquids and neuroendocrine parameters

Chemical factors R	
Nitrogen Organic, mg/L	.926
Carbon Organic, mg/L	-.490
Endocrine parameters R	
Triiodothyronine, nM/L	.834
(Nap/Kp) 0.5 as Mineralocorticoid Activity	.335
Glomerular Zone of Adrenal Cortex, μ M	-.389
(Cap/Pp) 0.5 as Parathyroid Activity	-.351
(Cap•Pu/Pp•Cau) 0.25 as Parathyroid Activity	-.307
Testosterone, nM/L	.213

Estados r

Corg has an inhibitory effect on the plasma level of testosterone ($r=-0.25$), instead, stimulating basal mineralocorticoid activity ($r=0.19$).

Taken together, both markers of organic substances determine endocrine status by 39% (Fig. 72).

$R=0.626$; $R^2=0.391$; $\hat{y}^2(12)=26$; $p=0.011$; $\hat{y} \text{ Prime}=0.544$

Fig. 72. Canonical correlation between the content of organic nitrogen and carbon in liquids (X axis) and endocrine parameters of rats loaded with them (Y axis)

The immune root is represented by parameters that are dependent on the activating factor (NK and B-lymphocytes, PN, the intensity of monocyte phagocytosis, the mass of the spleen and entropy of the splenocytogram) or suppressor (blood 0-lymphocytes, endotheliocytes thymus) exposure to organic nitrogen and activating (intensity of phagocytosis neutrophils) or suppressor (reticulocytes and fibroblasts of the spleen) influence organic carbon (Table 20).

Table 20. The factor structure of the canonical correlation between the roots that represent the content of organic nitrogen and carbon liquids and immunity parameters

Chemical factors R	
Nitrogen Organic (mg/L)	.876
Carbon Organic (mg/L)	-.588
Immune parameters R	
Natural Killer Lymphocytes, %	.583
Microbial Count of Monocytes, B/Ph	.441
B-Lymphocytes, %	.314
Stub Neutrophils of Blood, %	.292
Entropy of Splenocytogram	.249
Spleen Mass Index, mg/100 g BM	.163
0-Lymphocytes, %	-.351
Endotheliocytes of Thymus, %	-.296
Microbial Count of Neutrophils, B/Ph	-.691
Reticulocytes of Spleen, %	.334
Fibroblasts of Spleen, %	.315

The degree of determination of this immune constellation by organic substances reaches 77% (Fig. 73).

Table 22. Factor structure of the canonical correlation between the roots that represent the content of liquid microelements and immune parameters of the thymus, spleen and blood

Trace elements	R
H2SiO3	-0.737
Br -	-0.689
H3BO3	-0.674
J -	-0.672
F -	-0.287
Immune parameters	R
Microbial Count of Neutrophils, B/Ph -0.674	
Segmented Neutrophils of Blood, % -0.414	
Endotheliocytes of Thymus, % -0.345	
0-Lymphocytes, % -0.321	
Leukocytes of Blood, 10 ⁹ /L -0.284	
Lymphoblasts of Thymus, % -0.201	
Natural Killer Lymphocytes, % 0.578	
Fibroblasts of Spleen, % 0.361	
Reticulocytes of Spleen, % 0.322	
B-lymphocytes, % 0.246	
Phagocytic Index of Monocytes, % 0.170	

ishanes

$R=0.919$; $R^2=0.844$; $\hat{y}^2(100)=133$; $p=0.016$; $\hat{y} \text{ Prime}=0.020$

Fig. 75. Canonical correlation between the roots representing the content of trace elements in liquids (X axis) and immune parameters (Y axis)

Instead, the electrolyte determination of the endocrine status is revealed weak (33%), while the major components of most mineral waters are Na Cl - and HCO₃ - - turned out to be outside the canonical model (Table 23 and Fig. 76).

Estrodiol

Table 23. Factor structure of the canonical correlation between the roots that represent the content of fluid electrolytes and endocrine parameters

Electrolytes	R
Approx $2+$	.943
SO_4^{2-}	.934
Mg^{2+}	.781
Endocrine parameters	R
Triiodothyronine, nM/L .886	
Fascicular Zone of Adrenal Cortex, $\bar{y}M$.669	
(Nap/Kp) 0.5 as Mineralocorticoid Activity .525	
($\bar{y}p \cdot \bar{y}p$) -0.5 as Calcitonin Activity -.643	
Adrenal Mass Index, % -.188	

$R=0.577$; $R^2=0.333$; $\bar{y}^2(15)=24.5$; $p=0.057$; $\bar{y} \text{ Prime}=0.561$

Fig. 76. Canonical correlation between the roots representing the content of electrolytes in liquids (axis X) and endocrine parameters (Y axis)

Electrolyte determination of immunity is estimated at 66%, while it is found minimal, but significant influence of bicarbonate (Table 24 and Fig. 77).

Table 24. Factor structure of the canonical correlation between the roots that represent the content of fluid electrolytes and endocrine parameters

Electrolytes	Root 1
Approx $2+$	0.937
SO_4^{2-}	0.834
Mg^{2+}	0.353
HCO_3^-	-0.119
Immune parameters	Root 1
0-Lymphocytes, % 0.468	
B-Lymphocytes, % 0.451	
Stub Neutrophils of Blood, % 0.381	
Monocytes of Blood, % 0.378	
Microbial Count of Monocytes, B/Ph 0.355	
Basophiles of Blood, % 0.341	
Natural Killer Lymphocytes, % 0.308	
Killing Index of Neutrophils, % 0.178	

Microbial Count of Neutrophils, B/Ph -0.432	
Thymus Mass Index, mg/100 g BM -0.301	
Endotheliocytes of Thymus, %	-0.288
Phagocytosis Index of Neutrophils, % -0.189	
Lymphocytes of Spleen, %	0.216

$$R=0.812; R^2=0.659; \hat{y} = 0.110x + 0.110 \quad (56)=87; p=0.005; \hat{y} \text{ Prime}=0.110$$

Fig. 77. Canonical correlation between the roots representing the content of electrolytes in liquids (axis X) and immune parameters (Y axis)

If we superimpose the obtained experimental and clinical-physiological data observations on the matrix-scheme of currently existing ideas about agonists and receptor blockers of neurons, immunocytes and endocrinocytes, as well as microbiota, and the interaction of everyone with everyone, you can get a fairly complete picture of the mechanism of action adaptogens of various nature.

At least three effectors of adaptogens are polyphenols, fatty acids and bacteria (together they are a synbiotic) through the corresponding receptors (Ah, GP40/120, TL/NL) affect neurons of the enteric nervous system (ENS) and immunocytes gut-associated lymphoid tissue (GALT), as well as cells microbiota. The neurotransmitters and cytokines released under this influence, in turn, have autocrine and paracrine effects on the same or neighboring neurons and immunocytes, and also on the neurons of the autonomic and central nervous systems, reaching them through blood and irritating the afferent terminals n. vagus and n. splanchnicus. Next, the corresponding cortical and subcortical nerve structures act as a modulator impact on both bone marrow, thymus, spleen, lymph nodes and again immunocytes GALT (as well as SALT, BALT, MALT), and on endocrinocytes at least in the cortex adrenal glands, gonads and thyroid gland, the hormones of which, in turn, affect on immunocytes. A direct influence of polyphenols and fatty acids on endocrinocytes and blood/lymph immunocytes. Microbiota cells are under the influence

polyphenols and/or other organic substances, which act as prebiotics, begin to multiply intensively, as a result of which production increases and their release of fatty acids and endogenous AhR agonists, which are potentiated effects of exogenous agents on neurons, immunocytes and endocrinocytes. Others the consequence of activating the proliferation of microbiota is the strengthening of its immunomodulatory action, as well as antimicrobial action against pathogenic microflora and strengthening the barrier against the last one The effect of adaptogens is the normalization or minimization of disorders the state (or even optimization) of the neuro-endocrine-immune complex, and the final as a result, suppression or resolution of chronic inflammation of the digestive organs and genitourinary systems with improvement or normalization of their functional state.

A diagram by Chavan SS, Pavlov VA, and Tracey KJ [2017] illustrates the pathways transmission of information from adaptogen effectors to the central nervous system (Fig. 78).

Fig. 78. Anatomy of sensory neurons with a role in neuroimmune interaction [Chavan SS, Pavlov VA, and Tracey KJ, 2017]

Sensory neurons with cell bodies in the dorsal root ganglia are somatosensory and visceral. Somatosensory neurons innervating the skin and visceral neurons innervating the gastrointestinal tract enter the spinal cord through the dorsal horn. In the spinal cord, the central axonal endings of these neurons

establish synaptic contacts with interneurons and relay neurons that transmit signals to the brainstem and other areas of the brain. The sensory neurons of the vagus nerve originate in the nodal ganglia and innervate the gastrointestinal tract and other visceral organs. Most of their central axons terminate in the nucleus tractus solitarius (NTS) with projections to other areas of the stem and forebrain. The activity of somatosensory and visceral neurons, which transmit peripheral information to the central nervous system, changes in inflammatory and autoimmune conditions that affect innervated areas in visceral and somatic organs and

fabrics

The following scheme of Chavan SS, Pavlov VA, and Tracey KJ [2017] illustrates the ways of transmitting information from the central nervous system to components of the neuro-endocrine-immune complex, as well as internal organs (Fig. 79).

Fig. 79. Anatomy of efferent autonomic neurons with a role in immune regulation [Chavan SS, Pavlov VA, and Tracey KJ, 2017] Efferent neurons of the vagus nerve originate in the dorsal motor nucleus of the vagus nerve (DMN), and the nucleus ambiguus (NA) originates in the medulla oblongata. brain brain stem. These preganglionic cholinergic neurons project to visceral organs in the thoracic and abdominal cavities, particularly the gastrointestinal tract. They interact with postganglionic vagus neurons near or within the innervated organs, and these neurons release mainly acetylcholine. Preganglionic neurons of the vagus nerve also terminate in the abdominal ganglia and the superior mesenteric ganglion, where the splenic nerve originates. Catecholaminergic neurons of the splenic nerve release norepinephrine (NE) in the spleen. NE interacts with γ_2 -adrenergic receptors of choline acetyltransferase (ChAT)+CD4 + T cells and causes the release of acetylcholine. The locus coeruleus (LC) and the rostroventrolateral medulla (RVLM) are brain regions associated with sympathetic control. The RVLM gives descending projections to the sympathetic neurons of the spinal cord. Sympathetic preganglionic (cholinergic) fibers project to the paravertebral (not shown) and prevertebral ganglia, including the abdominal ganglia. Postganglionic fibers release predominantly norepinephrine (NE) in innervated visceral organs. Postganglionic fibers from the perivertebral ganglia innervate visceral organs, in particular the gastrointestinal tract. Sympathetic preganglionic fibers also innervate the adrenal medulla and stimulate epinephrine (Ep) secretion from chromaffin cells.

To visualize our ideas about the possible ways of influence of organic substances and autochthonous microflora of Naftusya water on neuroendocrine-immune complex, we will use the excellent review by Yoo BB & Mazmanian SK [2017] and their Fig. 80-82. The authors highlight new literature evidence that ENS has an important significance for microbe-induced immune responses in the gut. Proximity ENS to the immune system and its interaction with the external environment indicate that new paradigms of the functioning of the nervous system await discovery. ENS senses and responds to the dynamic ecosystem of the gastrointestinal tract by converting chemical signals from the environment into neural impulses that travel throughout the gut and to other organs in the body, including the CNS.

Receptors on enteric neurons mediate important functions of the gastrointestinal tract. Chemoreceptors respond to various chemical stimuli in the lumen, such as pH, osmolarity, and nutrients, including mineral water components, especially organic substances as AhR agonists, and fatty acids as agonists GP receptors.

Extrinsic, sympathetic and parasympathetic nerve fibers are included in gastrointestinal tract through the mesentery and can spread through all layers intestinal tissue. Myenteric and submucous plexus form a dense the nerve network that innervates the gastrointestinal tract along its entire length and depth Various immune cells are located in the muscularis, but also in the large amount in own plate, especially in Peyer's patches and lymphoid follicles These immune cells are also in close proximity to neurons and

glia. Among the cells with which microbes interact, we are most interested enteroendocrine cells (EEC). UES produces various modulators neuroendocrine molecules. These cells are commonly referred to as gut "taste" cells because they are known for their chemosensation and production molecules that control aspects of digestive system functions, such as gastric and pancreatic secretion, cholekinetics, etc. The influence of BAVN on HEPES was a subject of our very first study (Fig. 1).

Extrinsic nerves, intrinsic neurons and intestinal glial cells are located in close proximity to each other and to the immune cells of the gastrointestinal tract (Fig. 82). Thus, molecules produced by one cell can affect another cell, given that the latter expresses the receptor for molecule recognition. According to these parameters, theoretically interaction between neurons/glia and immune cells is sufficient, and some of these of predicted interactions are presented here. Immune cells can be affected neurotransmitters and neuropeptides produced by interneurons ENS (as well as those produced by external nerve fibers), a cytokines produced by immune cells can have the opposite effect on neurons [Yoo BB & Mazmanian SK, 2017].

Fig. 80. Anatomy of the gastrointestinal tract [Yoo BB & Mazmanian SK, 2017]

Fig. 81. Interactions at the intestinal epithelium [Yoo BB & Mazmanian SK, 2017] The intestinal epithelium is a site where luminal components are actively or passively transported into the tissue. Extrinsic nerves and neurons are in close proximity to the epithelium, and thus molecules that cross the epithelium and those secreted basolaterally can potentially influence their activity. Microbes or parts of microbes can cross the epithelium and affect other cell types via M cells, immunoglobulin-mediated transcytosis, goblet cell-associated passageways (GAPs), and general epithelial leakage. Dendritic cells (DCs) and macrophages can phagocytose microbial antigens and secrete cytokines that can also affect neurons. Parasympathetic fibers release acetylcholine (ACh) and induce the secretion of intracellular stores of molecules. In goblet cells, ACh also increases the rate of luminal selection of constant flux through the GAP. EECs can also release neuroendocrine molecules in response to stimulation by TLRs and short-chain fatty acids (SCFAs). These basolaterally released molecules can potentially regulate neuronal activity. Enteric glial cells can also project toward the epithelium, potentially allowing microbes to influence their function. Enteric neurons can be activated by commensal and pathogenic bacteria as well as SCFAs that diffuse across the epithelium.

Fig. 82. Interactions between immune cells of the gastrointestinal tract and ENS [Yoo BB & Mazmanian SK, 2017]

In our opinion, the key consequence of the effect on macrophages of microbes (via TL and NL receptors) and organic substances (via Ah, GP receptors) of drinking treatment water is the release of pro-inflammatory cytokines by macrophages. To visualize the following processes, we used an excellent illustration (Fig. 83) by Pavlov VA & Tracey KJ [2012]. Cytokines through chemosensitive glomus cells localized along autonomic nerves activate the endings of vagus afferents and through

them the nucleus tractus solitarius (NTS), more precisely, its dorsal-medial part (dmNTS). From the dmNTS, the common path in the integrative center goes to the parasympathetic and sympathetic branches. On the parasympathetic branch of the dmNTS, neurons project to the dorsal motor nucleus of the vagus nerve (DMN), nucleus ambiguus (NA) and area postrema (AP). Neuronal interconnections between the NTS, AP, DMN, NA, and higher forebrain regions (not shown) integrate afferent signaling and efferent immunoregulatory output mediated by the vagus nerve. Vagus cholinergic efferent output to the spleen, liver, and gastrointestinal tract (blue) regulates immune activation and inhibits the release of proinflammatory cytokines (dashed red lines).

Fig. 83. Functional anatomy of the anti-inflammatory reflex [Pavlov VA & Tracey KJ [2012]

This efferent cholinergic link of the inflammatory reflex can be activated in the brain using muscarinic-mediated mechanisms

acetylcholine receptor (mAChR) triggered by mAChR ligands and acetylcholinesterase (AChE) inhibitors such as galantamine. We

emphasize the fact that the same efferent vagus nuclei innervate heart, so heart rate variability simultaneously reflects vagal effects on the heart and other organs, including the immune and digestive

systems. On the other hand, the sympathetic branch projects to the caudal ventrolateral medulla and then to the rostral ventrolateral medulla, the signal from the nuclei of which enter the ganglion coeliacum, and from there to N-cholinergic receptors. spleen macrophages.

We consider the concept of "immunological" to be the apotheosis of the above homunculus" Tracey KJ [2007] (fig. 84).

Fig. 84. Scheme of the immunological homunculus [Tracey KJ, 2007]

According to the author of the concept, there is a structured, somatotopically organized neural network that controls specific components of the immune response through connection of input and output. Such a theoretical organization is similar to the classical one homunculus, which demonstrates that certain areas of the brain control certain parts body, and in the future it will be possible to build an "immunological homunculus". For example, one area of the brain can control cytokine responses in the liver, a

the other - activation of T cells in the spleen or lymph nodes. Some centers may integrate antigen presentation information, while others may integrate process information maturation of dendritic cells. Separate neurological domains in the central the nervous system can regulate the state of general readiness of the inborn immunity to respond to pathogens or damage. Existence of neuroanatomical maps of the cholinergic anti-inflammatory reflex is a significant step towards identification of other domains in the immunological homunculus, which is crucial for maximum protection of the body and health support during immune answers However, in subsequent publications of this laboratory [Pavlov VA & Tracey KJ, 2012; Chavan SS & Tracey KJ, 2017; Chavan SS et al., 2017], this hypothesis does not developed And only in 2018 was there a mention of it in the review of the authors [Pavlov VA et al., 2018], but unfortunately without clarification.

Please note that the author's scheme (Fig. 84) is at the end of each signature has a question mark (?), that is, it is not a statement, but a hypothesis. Under the influence of this hypothesis our laboratory conducted research to verify it [Kul'chyn's'kyi AB, Popovych IL et al., 2016;2017;2017a;2017b;Popovych IL et al., 2017;2018; Mel'nyk OI, Popovych IL et al., 2019].

How do the results obtained in our study (Table 25) fit into immunological homunculus concept/hypothesis?

Table 25. Agreed and divergent propositions of the immunological homunculus

EEG and Immune Variables	EEG and Immune response	EEG and Immune Variables	EEG and Immune response
Tracey's hypothesis		Tracey's hypothesis	
Activation of memory B cells		Late cytokine release	
Fp2- $\dot{\gamma}$ PSDr	-0.26 $\pm$ 0.12	P4- $\dot{\gamma}$ PSDr	+0.34 $\pm$ 0.17
IgM	-0.39 $\pm$ 0.22	P4- $\dot{\gamma}$ PSDr	-0.34 $\pm$ 0.12
IgA	-0.24 $\pm$ 0.14	O2- $\dot{\gamma}$ PSDr	-0.33 $\pm$ 0.13
		Interleukin-1	-0.42 $\pm$ 0.27
		C-reactive Protein	-0.26 $\pm$ 0.06
Tracey's hypothesis	Popovych's hypothesis		
T cell regulation	T cell regulation?		
T6- $\dot{\gamma}$ PSDr -0.25 $\pm$ 0.12	Fp2- $\dot{\gamma}$ PSDa +3.13 $\pm$ 1.56		
CD3 +CD25 + T-regulatory Lym +0.51 $\pm$ 0.19	Fp1- $\dot{\gamma}$ PSDa +3.14 $\pm$ 1.59		
CD3 +CD8 + T-cytolytic Lymph +0.60 $\pm$ 0.26	F3- $\dot{\gamma}$ PSDa +2.53 $\pm$ 1.34		
Popovych's hypothesis	F8- $\dot{\gamma}$ PSDa +7.62 $\pm$ 3.11		
Activation of Phagocytosis?		F7- $\dot{\gamma}$ PSDr +0.29 $\pm$ 0.12	
O2- $\dot{\gamma}$ PSDr +0.42 $\pm$ 0.17	F8 PSD Entropy -0.46 $\pm$ 0.21		
Microbial Count vs E. coli +0.40 $\pm$ 0.17	CD3 +CD25 + T-regulatory +0.51 $\pm$ 0.19		
Microbial Count vs St. aureus +0.39 $\pm$ 0.13	CD3 +CD8 + T-cytolytic +0.60 $\pm$ 0.26		
Killing Index vs Staph. aureus +0.79 $\pm$ 0.20			
Killing Index vs E. coli +0.65 $\pm$ 0.12			
Bactericidity vs E. coli +1.64 $\pm$ 0.39			
Bactericidity vs Staph. aureus +1.54 $\pm$ 0.42			
CIC +0.43 $\pm$ 0.13			

As can be seen from the comparative table. 25, in the supposed cortical center activation of memory B cells, inhibition of the activity of γ -rhythm generating neurons is accompanied by a decrease in the content of immunoglobulins M and A in the blood.

Center for late release of cytokines, according to Tracey KJ [2007], is designed between the parietal and occipital loci. This is consistent with our data on the connection of a decrease in the levels of IL-1, as well as C-reactive protein with suppression of γ -rhythm generating neurons in the O2 and P4 loci, simultaneously with activation of neurons located there that generate γ -rhythm. If we accept that

the cortical center of regulation of T-lymphocytes is projected onto locus T6, it turns out that it has an inhibitory effect on the level of T-regulatory and T-cytolytic lymphocytes in the blood. At the same time, the data we received give reasons to put forward an alternative hypothesis regarding the activating regulation of T lymphocytes by neurons generating γ - and δ -rhythms, which are projected onto prefrontal loci. Finally, our

humble contribution to the immunological homunculus concept is this hypothesis about localization in the right occipital part of the cerebral cortex generating γ -rhythm neurons responsible for the regulation of phagocytosis.

CONCLUSIONS

Based on experimental and clinical-physiological results research during 1988-2023 solved an important scientific problem - created a theory of the curative and preventive action of the resort's balneoids Truskavets, xenobiotic-synbiotic according to the active principles and neuro-endocrine-immune adaptogenic according to the mechanism of their implementation and essence.

In the process of creating the theory, new data were obtained, which are important theoretical and practical significance. 1.

Ambiguous and contradictory data about correlations between electroencephalogram (EEG) parameters and heart rate variability (HRV), which reflects functional relationships between the central and autonomic nervous systems.

2. The concept of the immunological homunculus is filled with new facts. In particular, the EEG loci on which nerve structures responsible for the regulation of phagocytosis of gram-positive and gram-negative cells are projected bacteria Information about EEG loci, already known earlier as responsible for other immune processes, supplemented with data on the type of rhythms generated nervous structures that project to these loci, as well as about the inhibitory or the activating nature of the regulation.

3. The concept of neuroendocrine-immune has gained further development complex by quantitative and qualitative integral assessment of the declared previous authors of the relationships between the parameters of nervous, endocrine and immune system. On this basis, the concept was significantly supplemented and specified general adaptation reactions of the organism (ZARO). In particular, it is proposed the author's leukocyte indices of adaptation and stress for quantitative assessment qualitatively different ZARO of stress, reactivation, as well as disharmonious and harmonious reactions of training, calm and increased activation. Existing for classic criteria of leukocytogram and levels in the blood to identify the type of ZARO glucocorticoid, mineralocorticoid, thyroid and sex hormones supplemented with calcitonin and HRV, EEG and immunity parameters.

4. Physiological correlates of known information parameters were revealed: harmony, synchronization and entropy - and applied them for integral assessment the state of the human and rat body and the influence of pathogenic and sanogenic agents on it factors 5.

It was found that the inhibitory or activating nature of the vagal influence on the level of pro-inflammatory cytokines in the blood is determined by the constellation of the initial ones parameters of the neuroendocrine-immune complex and the metabolome and may be reliably predicted using the obtained classification functions due to discriminant analysis. This solves the problem existing in the literature controversy along the lines of the concept of the cholinergic anti-inflammatory reflex.

6. Experiments with simulation of chronic aversive stress revealed three variants of immune responses, which are accompanied by characteristic changes in the parameters of the autonomic nervous and endocrine systems, which are significantly correlated with each other within the framework of the neuro-endocrine-immune complex.

7. In experiments on rats, it was shown that the preventive weekly use of BAVN, in general, similar to the reference adaptogen ginseng, limits, nullifies, reverses the neuro-hormonal, metabolic and immune pathogenic manifestations of acute stress and enhances its sanogenic properties, without significantly affecting on indicators that are not subject to stressor action. This is accompanied by minimization of the depression of the ST junction and the T wave of the ECG and erosive-ulcerative lesions of the gastric mucosa. The stress-mitigating effect of BAVN is reproduced by organic substances released from it, and when entering the body both orally and parenterally.

8. In a comparative experiment, the similarity of the stress-limiting effects of the domestic phytocomposition "Balsam of Crimea" with such ginseng and BAVN was found, which gave reason to patent it as an adaptogenic agent. The clinical and physiological observations demonstrated the possibility of increasing the effectiveness of the balneotherapy complex of the Truskavets resort by adding phytoadaptogens to its composition.

9. It was found that the preventive use of Truskavetska bottled water, which contains organic substances, but is devoid of microflora and the fatty acids produced by it, affects a number of post-stress parameters of the neuroendocrine-immune complex, metabolome, ECG and gastric mucosa of rats, similar to Naftusya water. At the same time, another constellation of parameters changes in the opposite way, on the basis of which the separate contributions of oil-like organic substances and the bacteria/fatty acid complex to the stress-limiting effects of Naftusya water are estimated.

10. In an experiment using tap water, Naftusya water and culture liquid filtered from microbes, which contains products of biotransformation of hydrocarbons of water-bearing rocks of the Truskavets deposit by the culture of hydrocarbon-oxidizing bacteria previously isolated from Naftusya, polyvariance of the own effects of organic substances (OR) and Naftusya microbes was revealed. In particular, both factors have comparable stimulating effects on the mass of the thymus, the content of plasma cells in the spleen, B- and theophylline-sensitive T-lymphocytes in the blood, as well as phagocytosis by neutrophils/microphages of *Staph. aureus*. Levels in the blood of leukocytes in general and eosinophils in particular and lymphoblasts in the spleen increase under the influence of OR only, and on the level of theophylline-resistant T-lymphocytes in the blood and reticulocytes in the thymus, as well as the thickness of the fascicular layer of the adrenal cortex, OR has a stimulating effect, and bacteria - an inhibitory effect. Instead, OPs reduce the thickness of the reticular layer of the adrenal cortex, inhibit phagocytosis by monocytes/macrophages of *Staph. aureus*, reduce the content of plasma cells in the thymus, as well as ordinary *E. coli* and

her strain with hemolytic ability in feces, while these parameters are not influenced by Naftusi bacteria. Instead, Naftusi bacteria cause a significant increase in the content of Bifidobacteria and Lactobacilli probiotics in feces, as well as lymphocytes in the thymus, while the effect of OR on these parameters is the opposite. Finally, the content of macrophages in the thymus under the influence of Naftusi bacteria decreases, while ORs are ineffective. 11. By giving rats tap water, native Naftusa, that is, with living microflora, as

well as Naftusa, in which the microflora was killed by ultraviolet irradiation or removed by filtering through a special sieve, the roles and contributions of OR, living microbes and their antigens in metabolic, endocrine and immunotropic effects of this healing water. It was found that the bactericidal ability of blood macrophages, the activity of two serum aminotransferases, and the concentration of sodium in urine are influenced unidirectionally, but differently by all three factors of Naftusi: to a minimum extent, OR, and to a maximum extent, live bacteria. On the other hand, lipopolysaccharides (LPS) of bacteria affect the intensity of macrophage phagocytosis, the content of macrophages in the splenocytogram, as well as its entropy somewhat more significantly than live bacteria. The stimulating effect of live bacteria on the mass of the spleen and the content of reticulocytes in it, and the mass of the thymus and the content of lymphocytes, lymphoblasts, reticulocytes and endotheliocytes in it is noticeable, while their LPS is barely expressed, on the other hand, the OR does not affect the listed parameters of immunity, and the content of reticulocytes in the spleen even reduce Live bacteria increase the level of leukocytes in the blood in general and especially of natural killers, as well as the content of monocytes in the spleen, on the other hand, their LPS moderately reduce these parameters, and OR occupy an intermediate position in terms of effect. At the same time, nocturnal diuresis and excretion of 17-CS, the serum level of medium-molecular-weight polypeptides (MMM), as well as the activity of hydroxylation and tubular secretion increase to the greatest extent under the influence of OR. The effects on the listed metabolic parameters of both live and killed bacteria are ambiguous. The negative effect of LPS on the content of bilirubin in the serum, in the splenocytogram of lymphocytes and lymphoblasts, as well as the phagocytic activity of blood monocytes/macrophages is pronounced, while the effect of live bacteria and AR is uncertain. 12. In the process of 3-month monitoring of the Truskavetsky Naftusya water field, significant fluctuations in both the composition and activity of the water of 8 wells were ascertained. The canonical correlation between the content of the constellation of organic substances in the water, on the one hand, and its effect on the physiological parameters of rats, on the other, proves that organic carbon, amines, bitumens, oxidizability and, to a lesser extent, polyphenols, determine the motility of the portal vein, microsomal hydroxylation, tubular secretion, choleresis and enteral absorption of water by

52%. 13. By the method of canonical correlation analysis of relationships between indicators of the chemical composition of natural potable medicinal waters and their artificial saline waters

analogues, on the one hand, and indicators of the neuroendocrine-immune complex animals - on the other hand, it was found that the content of organic nitrogen and carbon in water determines the level of a number of endocrine parameters by 39%, and immune parameters by 77%. The rate of determination from the side of trace elements is 59% and 84%, on the other hand, from the side electrolytes 33% and 66%, respectively.

14. In the clinical and physiological observation, it was found that a number parameters of the neuroendocrine-immune complex changes uniformly under by the influence of the course of use of both BAVN and phytoadaptogens, as well as transcutaneous electrical stimulation of nerve plexuses with the author's device "VEB". This additionally indicates the involvement of the nervous system in the mechanism of action BAVN.

15. In a comparative clinical and physiological study with a weekly using BAVN (as a complex of at least polyphenols, fatty acids and autochthonous bacteria), domestic phytocomposition "Balsam Truskavets" (as a complex of at least polyphenols and fatty acids) and ozokerite extract (as sources of polyphenols/aryl hydrocarbons) constellations of parameters were revealed of the neuroendocrine-immune complex, which change to the same extent, on the other hand, the reactions of other constellations of parameters are divergent. Received data made it possible to quantitatively evaluate individual ones by means of mathematical modeling contributions of polyphenols, fatty acids and autochthonous microflora of BAVN to its effects on the neuro-endocrine-immune complex, presumably mediated by Ah, GP40/120 and TL/NL receptors, respectively. 16. The results obtained document

full compliance

of Naftusya native water to the ISAPP criteria for classifying the agent as synbiotics: "a mixture containing living microorganisms and substrates, selectively used by host microorganisms, providing benefit to the owner's health".

17. Common reactions of the neuroendocrine-immune complex of rats were revealed for course watering with Naftusya water, applications of ozokerite, as well as a complex the use of both balneofactors, which are caused, presumably, by their influence oil-like organic substances, primarily aromatic, on arylhydrocarbon receptors of neuroterminals and/or lymphoid macrophages gut-associated tissue (GALT) or skin (SALT), respectively. This explains the absence of significant differences between integrals effects on the neuroendocrine-immune complex, on the one hand, and metabolism, leukocyturia, and bacteriuria, on the other hand, in patients with chronic pyelonephritis who received Naftusya bioactive water alone or in combination with applications ozokerite, as well as mineral fountains. 18. On the

basis of the obtained results, a theory of the curative and preventive action of the spa treatments of the Truskavets resort was created, xenobiotic-synbiotic according to the active principles and neuroendocrine-immune adaptogenic according to the mechanism of their implementation and essence.

The presented results are reflected in the following publications
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